

WATER HERITAGE IN THE VEXIN
MILL AND WASHHOUSES IN MONTALET-LE-BOIS

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Sustainable COnservation and REstoration of built cultural heritage

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CONTENTS

CONTENTS	2
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	4
INTRODUCTION	4
HISTORY AND LOCATION	5
1. History and folklore of Montalet-le-Bois, a village in the French Vexin region	5
a. Montalet-le-Bois, a small rural village.....	5
b. Lifestyle in the Vexin Français : before and after electricity and running water	7
2. Waterpower at the service of mankind; presentation of Montalet-le-Bois' hydraulic network...	10
a. Watercourses.....	10
b. Laundries	13
c. Mill.....	15
DIAGNOSIS.....	18
1. Description of infrastructures	18
a. Lavoir de la source.....	18
b. Lavoir des Férets.....	19
c. Lavoir rue de l'Eglise	20
d. Hydraulic mill wheel	22
2. Alterations	22
a. Lavoir de la source.....	22
b. Lavoir des Férets.....	24
c. Lavoir rue de l'Eglise	32
d. Hydraulic mill wheel	39
PRESERVATION AND ENHANCEMENT PROJECT	41
1. Preservation and restoration of structural elements.....	41
a. Laboratory tests.....	41
b. Consolidation of the actual infrastructures.....	41
2. Enhancement project	45
a. Promoting water-related heritage: a water trail.....	45
b. Reusing water to generate electricity; restoring the mill wheel	48

c. Urban development.....	50
3. Project costing and implementation	66
CONCLUSION	68
SOURCES.....	70
APPENDIX.....	75

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We would also like to thank the Parc naturel régional du Vexin Français, which has supported us in this project and is as keen as we are to see it come true.

INTRODUCTION

In this project, we are focusing on the water heritage of Montalet-le-Bois’ village in the Yvelines. We have studied three washhouses (lavoirs) and an ancient mill in the commune, all of which are powered by the Bernon river. This small-scale heritage existing all around France, linked to water, is also important, reminding us of the relationship with water before the arrival of other sources of energy and running water. In this report, we will attempt to explain its history and uses. This heritage is of particular interest in Montalet-le-Bois, as the village is crossed by ditches that supply fountains, washhouses, mills, etc., and are controlled by sluice gates.

Studying these ancient infrastructures, as part of a network that structures the whole of Montalet-le-Bois, has been very rewarding, and has given us the enthusiasm for a study and enhancement project that will benefit the whole village.

In this paper, we will begin by outlining the historical context of Montalet-le-Bois and the way of life in the French Vexin over the centuries, while explaining the role of the washhouses and mills in communal life and how they are working. We will then share our sanitary diagnosis of the three washhouses and the mill wheel, proposing restoration measures and finally including them in our village-wide enhancement project proposition.

HISTORY AND LOCATION

1. History and folklore of Montalet-le-Bois, a village in the French Vexin region

a. Montalet-le-Bois, a small rural village

Montalet-le-Bois is a village situated in the Yvelines, located near the Seine River between Arthies and Meulan-en-Yvelines, around fifty kilometers from Paris. The village has a population of 308, the majority of whom now belong to the executive and higher intellectual professions. Montalet-le-Bois remains a typical rural commune of the region, where until a few decades ago the population lived mainly from agriculture.

Location of Montalet-le-Bois in the Vexin – Source : geoportail.gouv.fr

Montalet-le-Bois is made up of several hamlets : the chief town of Montalet-le-Bois, the hamlet of Férets to the north, and Damply to the south, crossed by the D205. The village lies between two hills, the "côte aux filles" and the "côte aux moutons". It is crossed by the Bernon and the Férets brook, which joins the Bernon in the center of the village. These streams are tributaries of the Montcient, which joins the Aubette de Meulan and flows into the Seine at the border between Meulan and Hardricourt.

The village lies in the south of the Vexin Français, the Ile-de-France's part of the natural region that divides Normandy from the Ile-de-France. The ancient history of this area is demonstrated by the presence of vestiges dating back to the Neolithic period, shown in the archeology museum of Guiry-en-Vexin. Numerous Gallo-Roman vestiges also demonstrate the continuity of the occupation of this region from our era to the present day, including Gallic stone weapons found in Montalet-le-Bois during the 19th century ¹.

In the Middle Age, the parish of Montalet-le-Bois belonged to the archbishop of Rouen, controlled by the diocese of Versailles. The territory belonged to the lords of the region.

The village was traditionally relying on agriculture growing cereals, roots, vegetables and wicker. A few vines were implanted on the territory as well. Meadows were used for cattle breeding. In the 19th century, the village was involved in the cardoons' crop for the manufacture of weaving combs. Trade with neighboring towns kept the village going. Sand and limestone quarries provided supplies for the village's construction and industrial activities. Peat was also used as fuel. As we will see, the Bernon River and the Férets stream played a central role in the village's survival, contributing to agriculture and then, industry.

Montalet-le-Bois' population dropped slightly during the 19th and 20th centuries but has remained relatively stable with the arrival of people working in the tertiary sector, attracted by the commune's peaceful setting and proximity to larger conurbations and Paris.

¹ J 3211/15 [9], Montalet-le-Bois. Monographie communale de Paul Aubert, 1863 – 1949

b. Lifestyle in the Vexin Français : before and after electricity and running water

The Vexin Français has a long rural history, with people living off the land for centuries. Wheat, barley and rye are the main crops grown here. The “Musée de l’Outil” in Wy-dit-joli-Village is home to a collection of antique tools from the Vexin region, demonstrating the trades and needs of a traditional society. Blacksmith’s tools, forester’s saws, winegrower’s hoods, horse care utensils, weaving wheels... Just a few examples to illustrate the vast number of tools required for the survival of traditional Vexin society.

Life is organized according to the resources available in the village, and access to water is essential for village self-sufficiency. Cooking, washing clothes and household chores, farming and livestock breeding, as well as most craft production depends on the water resource. Therefore, springs and watercourses played a key role in determining the location of village communities. The Vexin was a propitious region for life thanks to its hydrography.

To clean laundry for example, women went to springs and beat the linen on flat stones or boards placed above the watercourses. Washing was done in vats beforehand. After soaking the linen for the first time, water was boiled and the linen was washed in basins and vats using ashes. The linen was then taken out, wrung out and brought to the washhouse in carts. The women rinsed the linen and beat it on the stones. The linen was then taken back to be dried.

In production, human power was used, but it was necessarily accompanied by animal power, which makes it possible to mechanize manufacturing processes and lighten working conditions. Animal power has always been used in agriculture and to power machinery.

The first systems using hydraulic energy to power various machines and mechanisms are dated from around the 13th century, as illustrated by illustrations from Villard de Honnecourt’s notebook showing hydraulic hammers and sawmill mechanisms.²

1

FIG. 2. — LA SCIE HYDRAULIQUE
DE VILLARD DE HONNECOURT, VERS 1230

2

Quand on le fait mouvoir de haut de bas on voit une roue
qui se tourne et on voit en dessous une marteau qui se
bat et on voit en dessous une marteau qui se bat.

² Album de Villard de Honnecourt, architecte du XIIIe siècle : reproduction de 66 pages et dessins du manuscrit français 19093 de la Bibliothèque nationale, ed. H. Omont, Paris : Berthaud, 1906.

Previous page: Illustrations of ancient mechanisms, Carnets de Villard de Honnecourt

1 Hydraulic saw

2 hydraulic hammer

This development enabled mass-production and significantly increased the rhythm of factories. Above all, it enabled continuous production, overcoming dependence on other resources such as wind and animal power.

These facilities, central to farming communities, were controlled by the lords in feudal times, for example through “Droit de l’eau” (Water right). It was granted to millers to harness the power of a river. In exchange, the miller owed the lord gifts, linked or not to his production. This was one of the few feudal rights to survive the French Revolution. It still exists today, but is very rarely granted, mainly for environmental reasons.

In the Vexin region, flour mills were essential to the cultivation of cereals, which led to the development of a large network of mills.

It was a simple mechanism, able to rotate a millstone. The millstone is a flat, solid cylinder used to grind grain. It is generally made of stone, and its motion is transmitted by a wooden axis of rotation that receives the movement of the wheel (or blades in the case of windmills) via toothed wheels and pinions.

Grain is poured into the millstone manually or with a hopper.

Schematic of a vertical wheel water mill's gear – Source : <http://blogpeda.ac.poitiers.fr-www2.ac-toulouse.fr>

These hydraulic systems were the first step towards the industrialization of production, which continued with the arrival of fossil fuels: coal and then oil.

While millers were used to adapt their production to the fluctuating situations, when a commodity or sector disappeared for example, most mills did not survive the late 19th and early 20th centuries and the arrival of coal in industry. To compete with coal-fired production, mills had to be located close to the biggest rivers.³

At this time mills of the Vexin mainly stopped their activity, as the territory was not crossed by a significant river. By the 1920s, flour mills had almost entirely disappeared. The Vexin lost population at this time, the remaining population still depending on agriculture.

Simultaneously to this mechanization enabled by waterways, social upheavals influenced access to drinking and non-drinking water used by village communities. In the 18th and 19th centuries, slow industrialization and health problems gave rise to a hygienist movement supported by the new government. It was at this time that most of France's washhouses were built. Thanks to the law of February 3, 1851, passed by the 2nd Republic, communes obtain subsidies to build models of public washhouses almost free of charge⁴.

Les laveuses, illustration of Jules Voegle, Strasbourg, 1851 – Source : gallica.bnf.fr

Progress in the twentieth century then largely reduced people's dependence on local water resources, although access to running water was slow, particularly in the remote villages of the Vexin region. In Montalet-le-Bois for instance. Mr. Dubois, a resident of a farm in Montalet-le-Bois whom we met during our study, had access to running water in the 1960s in his farmhouse. Today, access to running water and technology keeps industries outside villages and household appliances inside homes supplied by underground networks.

In Montalet-le-Bois, we are fortunate that these buildings have been well preserved and are still visible.

³ J. Briand, *Moulins et meuniers dans le Vexin et le Pays de Thelle*, ed. Le Pétillon, 1998, p. 16.

⁴ *Lavoir*, article published on Maisons Paysannes de France. URL : https://wiki.maisons-paysannes.org/wiki/Lavoir#cite_ref_1

2. Waterpower at the service of mankind; presentation of Montalet-le-Bois' hydraulic network

a. Watercourses

In Montalet-le-Bois, the Bernon's and Férets' creeks have always been the village's strength. The municipal monograph dated 1899 mentions the use of the watercourse in village life, whose water is described as "beautiful clear water". Its purity allowed it to be used for cooking and household purposes in Montalbois households⁵.

The creek of Bernon, coming from the north-west of the commune, is a 7km-long natural stream validated by SANDRE (Service d'administration national des données et référentiels sur l'eau). It rises in the commune of Lainville-en-Vexin and flows into the Montcient, a tributary of the Aubette-de-Meulan and the river Seine, in the commune of Seraincourt. The submerged part of the creek begins at one of the washhouses studied, in the commune of Montalet-le-Bois, which we have called Lavoir de la Source.

The Férets stream enters the commune from the north-east. It is 3 km long natural stream, also validated by the SANDRE under the name of "Ravine de la mare de Magny". It rises in the commune of Lainville-en-Vexin and flows into the Ru de la Bernon at the hamlet of Les Férets, near the village center. The course of this stream is sometimes blurred, as it regularly runs dry.

La Bernon

La Ravine de la mare de Magny (ruisseau des Férets)

Satellite imagery of Montalet-le-Bois' creeks – Source : www.sandre.eaufrance.fr

⁵ P 5, J 3211/15 [9], Montalet-le-Bois. Monographie communale de Paul Aubert, 1863 – 1949

The confluence of these two streams structures the village. A system of canals, operating with sluice gates at several points in the village, was set up to control the flow of the Bernon (confluence of the two streams) and guide it through the village. These canals are known as "biefs", and sometimes run in the open air, sometimes under infrastructure (roads, highways, etc.). This network is clearly visible on the Plan de cadastre from 1824.

Hydraulic system represented on the Plan de l'Administration du cadastre, 1824 (Archives départementales des Yvelines)

It seems that this system of diversion bays and sluices was built during the 19th century. Indeed, it does not appear on the 1782 intendance plan, on which the Bernon stream and the Férets stream do not meet at the same point. The branch of the Bernon, passing through the mill, does not appear on the plan.

Plan d'intendance de la paroisse de Montalet-le-Bois, 1782 (C45 21, Archives départementales des Yvelines)

In the 19th century, 25 habitants owned a spring in the village, while other households drew their water from wells and communal fountains, such as the fountain in rue de l'Eglise, located near a communal wash house.

b. Laundries

There were seven public washhouses, three of them were covered. The covered laundries are those in Les Férets and rue de l'Eglise that we studied. The other one is located on the road towards the hamlet of Damply. There were also private washhouses. Monsieur Dubois, for example, showed us the washhouse located in his meadow right next to the Férets communal wash house, which was used by his family. This washhouse consisted of a spring, and the laundry was traditionally beaten on a stone.

We have not been able to date the washhouses studied precisely, but we can put forward our hypotheses as to when they were built.

The oldest washhouse we studied was built at the Bernon spring. It already appears on the 1782 intendance plans. Its long, hemicircular shape is recognizable on the plan. It was an open-air washhouse that still belongs to the commune, as indicated in the "Etat de section" of 1826.

Etats de sections des propriétés non bâties et bâties, 1826 (3P3 1570, Archives départementales des Yvelines)

Plan d'intendance of the parish of Montalet-le-Bois, 1782 (C45 20, Archives départementales des Yvelines)

Women used to lean on the large stones of the basin to rinse and beat their laundry. It seems like its structure has almost not changed since its construction, its structure being very simple.

The other washhouses, Les Ferrets and Rue de l'Eglise, have a similar appearance and therefore seem to date from the same construction campaign. They do not appear on the plan d'intendance or on the plan cadastral of 1924. They do, however, appear on the renovated plan de cadastre of 1933.

This postcard shows the rue de l'Eglise's washhouse at the beginning of the 20th century.

Environs de Meulan, Montalet, Chemin de Montalet à Damply, postcard, ed. Klein (Meulan), 9 x 14 cm (Archives départementales des Yvelines 3Fi165 2 1900-1909)

They may well have been built during the washhouse construction campaigns that took place in the early second half of the 19th century, as their similar structure and the fact that they were perfectly adapted to their purpose and designed for the comfort of the washerwomen suggest. They feature a roof to protect from the sun or rain, and are semi-open, each with one or two low walls to protect the women from the elements and increase privacy. The sloping edges made it more comfortable to lean over the basins.

The structure of their basins is also specific. The Férets wash house has three multi-level basins, which enable the laundry to be separated during multiple rinses. This also made it possible to adapt to the level of the Férets stream, which had multiple periods of drought. The washhouse situated Rue de l'Eglise does not have a basin. Women used to rinse laundry directly in the bief of the Bernon.

Today these washhouses are made of cement, they were originally built of rubble with a wooden frame and pillars. Today, they belong to the Town Hall.

Au lavoir, Postcard, ed Klein (Meulan) – Source : Geneanet, mis en ligne par drake

c. Mill

There were two mills in Montalet-le-Bois: the Moulin des Près located in the hamlet of Damply, and the mill we have studied. It is located on the branch of the Bernon's creek and occupies a central position in the village. Today, it serves as the Mairie's offices, and its wheel is featured on the commune's coat of arms in the top left-hand corner. The town hall has made it an important element in demonstrating the heritage represented by the commune's hydraulic network.

Montalet-le-Bois' Coat of arms

We haven't been able to date the mill precisely; the only thing we know for sure is that it appears on the plan de cadastre of 1824. We think it must have been built at the same time as the development of the Bernon branch and reach. This millstream must have been built to operate the mill and control the rotation speed of the wheel and thus production. A gate is located just above the wheel.

Water gate above the wheel, personal picture, Mars 2023

It was a grain mill, for flour production, as the Matrice des section bâties from 1881 to 1908 mentions a machine for threshing grain when the mill. Mr. Denis François Laurent, owned the premises ⁶.

Plans de l'Administration du cadastre, 1824 (Archives départementales des Yvelines)

Laurent François	982	Propriété (bâtie)	1. 60	un	69
al	983	Maison			28
	984	Sol Bâtie	1. 60	unique	74
		Propriété			165
		Sol	2. 30	unique	7. 13

Etats de sections des propriétés non bâties et bâties, 1826 (3P3 1570, Archives départementales des Yvelines)

The grain was ground by the mill wheel, powered by the Bernon stream in conjunction with the Férets stream. The original mill wheel no longer exists, having been replaced by a dummy wheel in the 1990s. We therefore have little information on the wheel that was used at the time. However, the schoolteacher's monograph mentions the presence of a mechanic who owned a factory in the area that supplied the wheels for both Montalet-le-Bois' mills. He manufactured trough and bucket wheels ⁷. Our mill was equipped with a trough wheel system.

⁶ P 18, 3P3 1573 Matrice des propriétés bâties, 1881 – 1908

⁷ P 10, J 3211/15 [9], Montalet-le-Bois. Monographie communale de Paul Aubert, 1863 – 1949

The mill probably stopped to operate in the early 20th century, and its structure has deteriorated considerably through lack of maintenance.

In the 1980s, the town council moved into the old mill, buying the mill, the old barn and the miller's house from their owner (see article in Appendix 2). The purchase was made following a property seizure in 1983 and a declaration of public interest, which allowed the operation that would have been too expensive for the commune's budget. Since that time, the Town Hall has been housed in these premises and is responsible for its upkeep.

As the miller paid for the water rights when the mill was created, the commune still has the option of using the force of the water to operate the wheel and even exploit it for possible production.

Le moulin a surement cessé de fonctionner dans le début du XXème siècle, et son bâti s'est fortement dégradé par manque d'entretien.

Town hall with the mill's wheel – Source: Montalet-le-Bois's commune

DIAGNOSIS

In this section, all images are personal photographs taken during our two surveys on 10th of February and 24th of March 2023.

1. Description of infrastructures

a. Lavoir de la source

The wash house is located close to the departmental road n.o.205 at the source of the creek of Bernon. However, the building is in poor condition, with only a few features remaining.

We can make out a stone cladding partially covered with plaster, with an opening at the bottom to allow the creek's water to flow into the first basin. When the latter fills up, the water passes through an opening in the stone partition between the first and second basins. The water from the washtub then flows back into the stream towards the center of the village through a small opening in a concrete element at the end of the washtub path.

These installations are surrounded by a few stones surrounded by the vegetation. No facing or pathway is yet visible.

View from above

b. Lavoir des Férets

This washhouse is located in the rue des lavandières, close to the route des Férets. It is built parallel to the watercourse. The wash house is supplied with water by a pump connecting the creek to one of the basins. The latter is raised above the others so that the excess of water flows into the basin below through an opening in its edges. Subsequently, the one that received the water when it's full will discharge the liquid into the adjacent basin via the same means. Both basins are the same height, but the latter has a larger volume.

The wash house is bounded by two walls forming an "L" shape. These walls are made of red bricks covered with plaster. We can distinguish two different cement renderings. The first is a thin, dark-gray coating with a very fine grain size and a smooth finish. It appears to be cement mortar. Secondly, we see a thicker white layer with a coarse grain size and a rough finish. The white tint acquired by this pass is not natural; it seems to be the result of the application of white paint following the application of this rendering.

A concrete walkway leads to the basins. This access is bordered by beige-pink concrete kerbs. The basins have concrete floors and are surrounded by low concrete walls.

Finally, the wash house has a lean-to roof. The ridge purlin is placed on the wall running along the driveway and is barely visible. The other purlins and rafters are clearly visible. The eave purlin rests on two posts. One is wooden, the other metal. Metal fasteners are also visible on the roof structure. The rafters are covered with chipboard panels. Next, we can see that the roof is covered with small flat red Vexin tiles. Finally, the roof is clad with zinc edging along the wall and on the roadside.

View from above

Facing view

Side view

c. Lavoir rue de l’Eglise

This washhouse is located in Rue de l’Eglise close to the town hall. It also runs parallel to the watercourse that crosses the commune and empties a little further on at the mill wheel. The building is high up, and can only be reached by climbing a staircase. Unlike the other washhouses studied, this building has no basin. In fact, the wash house is positioned on the course of the river, so there's no need to build a reservoir.

It has a classic "U" shape, with the opening on the stream side. We can see that the facings are all covered with a coarse-grained cement rendering with a rough finish, like the Férets washhouse. However, the white paint finish is only visible on the inside. On the outside, the rendering has a beige tint. We can't distinguish all the materials that make up the walls of this washhouse. However, we can assume that the facings are built in the same way as those of the Férets washhouse. It is likely that these walls are made of red bricks, a fine cement rendering and then the rendering mentioned above. Two openings were made to allow circulation within the washhouse. The driveway also features a concrete slab.

Finally, the wash house has a lean-to roof that follows the slope of the washhouse's side walls. As for the roof structure, the ridge purlin is placed on the wall running along the street. It is covered with plaster, making it discreet. As for the eaves purlin, we find it leaning against the creek on both sides at the level of the side facings. Another intermediate purlin and the rafters are also visible. All this is covered with bitumen paper to reinforce the watertightness of the installation. The roof is covered with small, flat red Vexin tiles. Finally, zinc edges are installed on the sides of the roof.

Facing view

Side view 1

View from the back

Side view 2

d. Hydraulic mill wheel

The original wheel of Montalet-le-Bois' mill was replaced in the 1970s due to its poor condition. The replacement wheel is not working but it is used by the town to show the existence of the ancient mill. The current wheel, a new substitute wheel, had been installed in 2013. It was restored and maintained in 2017 and 2022 by volunteer work.

The wheel and its housing are made of wood. However, we note that the fixings and the axle are made of metal. The rest of the mechanism, including the spinning wheel, lantern and grinding wheels, is installed inside the town hall so we were unable to see it.

2. Alterations

During our site visits, we made observations to establish a diagnosis of the infrastructures. We have attempted to detail here the disorders encountered and the hypotheses as to their causes, based on which we have proposed our restoration project. We will also give some recommendations in the cases encountered.

a. Lavoir de la source

Cracking

The element used to evacuate water from this washhouse to the village stream is made of concrete, as described above. Cracks are visible on this piece.

We are dealing with an element composed of a cement matrix with no open-air protection, as we observed with the Férets and rue de l'Eglise washhouses. In this case, we're looking at the same possible origins for this deterioration: contamination by soluble and/or expansive salts, climatic hazards, etc.

This phenomenon of cracking can evolve until the element bursts at certain points. The problem if this happens is that pieces of concrete can block the drain from the washbasin into the watercourse. In addition, chunks of concrete may also fall into the watercourse, which is not recommended.

→ Stones

Erosion

We note that most of the stones in place delimiting the washhouse right-of-way are eroded.

At the time of our in-situ intervention, the stones were eroded and appeared stable, with no other alterations in progress. Nevertheless, we need to find the possible origin of the condition of the stones we now observe. These stones have been exposed to an aggressive, unprotected environment. Like concrete, the stones may have met salts via atmospheric pollution from the nearby road, fertilizers or even the soil itself. These salts will then crystallize within the stone, humidity permitting. This can lead to cracks, loss of material and granular disintegration. Subsequently, this erosion could be the result of biological colonization, which stores potential salts and water in contact with the stones. This perpetual proximity creates an imbalance in the material. Finally, the vagaries of the climate are likely to alter these stones. We can see this with sudden and significant variations in temperature, heavy rainfall, strong winds, etc. All these possible origins cause granular disintegration and loss of material to the stones, leading to the erosion we're seeing today.

Although there is no longer any active granular disintegration, the stones are still very exposed as they have lost their epidermis. Although their degradation will not progress very quickly, it should be monitored. Nous remarquons que la grande majorité des pierres en place délimitant l'emprise du lavoir sont érodées.

Biological colonization

The presence of biological colonies is visible throughout this washhouse. This phenomenon can be seen on the rest of the facings, edges and stone slabs.

We note that the stones in this washhouse are no longer protected; they are left in the open air. There's no protection to keep them out of the wind or water, which is why the biologically active colonies haven't been destroyed. The wind allowed the bacteria to reach the stones, and the rain allowed them to develop. What's more, the washery has been laid out in such a way as to blend into the topsoil. Nevertheless, there is no watertight seal between the stones and the topsoil, which is another way for biological colonies to reach these elements.

These biological colonies can be harmful to the stones. On the surface of the stone, these organisms can store salts from the atmosphere, as well as large quantities of water, which can damage the stone. Subsequently, these exogenous deposits can also create encrustation, deteriorating the balance of water transfer within the material. As the situation worsens, this can lead to disintegration. Nevertheless, the washhouse is in a very poor state of repair, and this deterioration has already worsened. The overall situation now seems stable, so the pathology will evolve more slowly, but the impact of the colonies on the stones will continue.

b. Lavoir des Férets

→ Walls

Soiling / Biological colonization

On a large proportion of the walls, we can see the presence of exogenous deposits (mosses, lichens, etc.) and soiling. Moreover, these phenomena are intensified on facings not protected by roofing or the like.

Dirt and biological colonies develop on facings when they are not properly maintained. What settles on the walls comes from the washerwoman's environment. We may therefore be able to find dust from houses or farms, pollution particles from vehicles passing through the village, bacteria close to lichens or mosses. All of this was carried in by the wind and settled in the wall cavities. Subsequent rainfall allows the various organisms to develop and spread dirt along the facing.

These foreign bodies can pose a problem for the cohesion of the rendering. Dirt can be loaded with soluble salts such as sulfate, which is harmful to cement, and biological colonies can store water, which can also contain aggressive salts. It would be worthwhile addressing this issue to avoid weakening the plaster or other elements.

Cracking

Inspecting the washhouse, cracks are visible directly on the cement mortar used to cover the bricks. This phenomenon can be seen on the wall at the entrance of the washhouse, in the layer beneath the finishing layer.

First of all, we can point to the actions of the environment. Climate can play a role in cement degradation, through freeze-thaw or other variations. The atmosphere, for its part, is also capable of bringing in particles harmful to this material. Soluble salts such as sulfate (from automobile pollution) can create secondary ettringite within the concrete matrix, which is an expansive salt that creates cracks and even splinters. Of course, this is just one possibility, but we may also find other salts that can degrade cement, such as potassium (soil) and/or sodium (fertilizer), which can cause an alkali-reaction within the cement by reacting with the aggregates. Subsequently, the difference in material between cement and brick can be the cause of cracking. These materials don't have the same properties, so they don't undergo expansion in the same way, which can lead to cracking. What's more, cement seems to have aged, so it's logical that it has become more porous and less resistant. This aging makes the material more vulnerable to any attack.

It's important to monitor the evolution of cracks in this material, as they can expand, causing the cement to burst and leaving the bricks exposed.

Material loss

The cement layers applied to the bricks are subject to material loss, leaving the bricks exposed. This phenomenon can be observed at the top of the wall on which the roof rests, as well as on the wall at the entrance to the washhouse.

This loss of material, which is perceptible in certain places, is the consequence of the cracking, which is worsening. The possible origins of this pathology are therefore the same as those of cracks.

What's more, this deterioration will expose the bricks to the atmosphere, leaving them unprotected. Consequently, if the bricks deteriorate because of this exposure, the stability of the walls will be called into question. So, it is important to pay close attention over the next few months to avoid any accidents.

Corroded fixings

On the façade of the washhouse, which runs parallel to the street, we can see some corroded metal fixings. These must have been used to hold tools essential to the life of the washhouse, or to place the planters we saw around the washhouse.

This is visible because these metal elements have not been protected. The roof does not cover them, and no treatment has been applied. As a result, they have been left in the open air and exposed to rain, leading to corrosion. The risk of this pathology is that the metal will acquire greater volume as it corrodes, bearing in mind that it is fixed in the cement. Over time, this will cause the plaster to crack at the screw points.

→ Floor

Cracking

On the concrete slab, we can see cracks both in the driveway to the washhouse and on the steps leading up to the building.

First, we are dealing with a material with a cementitious matrix just like the rendering, we have the same leads to possible origins. Furthermore, other origins can be envisaged for this pathology, as we are interested in a slab. Indeed, the laying of this concrete may also be the cause of these cracks. Within this washhouse, we note that this slab covers a large surface area, without any real expansion joints being made. As a result, the slab could have cracked under the effect of temperature variation. Subsequently, this phenomenon could also have been caused by the forces exerted by the plants underneath the slab.

For the time being, this deterioration does not represent a great danger, but if it were to worsen, there would be no cohesion within the slab, and visitors to the laundries could fall.

Vegetation

At step level of the entrance to the washhouse we note the presence of vegetation in the cracks.

The appearance of this vegetation indicates a potential oversight during the pouring of the concrete slab. If we can now observe this vegetation within the cracks, it's because there's no seal between the slab and the topsoil. So, as mentioned above, these organisms were able to push the slab underneath, creating these cracks. What's more, the fact that the slab is potentially in contact with the topsoil could add further constraints in terms of any salts present in the soil or humidity.

This wild vegetation adds to the risk of falls, since during rainy episodes, the slab could be more slippery than usual. What's more, the topsoil will also bring moisture and any harmful salts to the concrete.

Efflorescence

There are several areas of efflorescence in the cracks of the concrete slab.

This pathology shows the presence of soluble salts within the concrete. However, this does not allow us to establish which salt has affected the material. It is possible, however, to make some assumptions as to its nature. Previously, we had already suggested a number of possible sources: sulfate (automobile pollution), potassium (soil), sodium (fertilizer).

The fact that salts are contaminating the concrete slab means that its deterioration is likely to continue, with new cracks appearing and, in some places, even splintering. All this once again feeds the risk of falls within this washhouse.

→ Pond edges

Cracking

The pond edges are also made of concrete. Nonetheless, we note the existence of cracks in several places. We see them along the concrete slab and on the edges surrounding the basins.

We're dealing with a material that also has a cementitious matrix, like the plaster and slab of the open-air washhouse. Consequently, the potential origins of these cracks are the same as for the other elements mentioned. These edges are also in contact with water from the nearby stream. It's possible that water is another source of soluble salts harmful to concrete.

The problem that these cracks may cause in the future is bursting and loss of material. This could limit access to the washhouse, since without this safety feature, there is a risk of falling into the basins. As for the edges close to the watercourse, any loss of material could potentially clog up the water inlet and disrupt the village's ecosystem.

Efflorescence

Efflorescence can be seen in all the cracks along the edges of the basins in the washhouse lane.

As seen above, this pathology is evidence of the presence of soluble salts within the concrete. We can therefore confirm that these elements are also affected by the salts, as is the concrete slab, which may seem logical given their proximity.

Vigilance is required to monitor the deterioration of the kerbs. With the appearance of efflorescence, the risks remain the same. In the future, we could be faced with the risk of people falling and obstacles in the watercourse.

Material loss

Some of the concrete edges surrounding the basins are subject to material loss. This deterioration is the evolution of cracks when left untreated.

The cracks observed on these elements and the loss of material are linked, so it is logical to consider that their potential origins are the same. Nevertheless, certain possibilities can be ruled out, such as those involving the interface between 2 different materials and direct contact with the topsoil, which we have not observed in these kerbs.

As far as the risks associated with this pathology are concerned, there is always the risk of visitors falling due to a loss of cohesion within the material, and a risk of disturbance to the watercourse.

Soiling / Biological colonization

The edges of the basins, like many of the washhouse's structural elements, are directly exposed to the environment without any real protection. As a result, we have observed the presence of soiling and biological colonies all over the edges.

The origin and development of these pathologies are relatively similar to those observed on the washhouse facings. In fact, the composition of these exogenous deposits depends on the environment in which the building is located. We're dealing with other structural elements of the building, but we're still in the same place, so this could explain the potential similarity in their development and nature. However, water in contact with these edges may be a source of other types of exogenous deposits.

The spread of these disorders needs to be monitored, as they could have an impact on the concrete of the kerbstones. It could also contaminate the water in the basins in contact with the kerbstones. This would present a significant risk, as the water would then be discharged into the village stream.

Concrete patching

In some places around the site, we have noticed that the upper part of the concrete (pinkish tint) is different from the lower part (grey tint). The pink concrete must have been applied to repair the original concrete of the washhouse. In the places where we can see this patching, we can see that the boundary between the two materials is not continuous. This shows that the concrete in the upper section was not laid when the wash house was built, and that the concrete in the lower section must have shattered or disintegrated to have such a variable surface. What's more, the repair work does not appear to have been

carried out recently. Biological colonization can be observed on the pink-tinted concrete, showing that it has been in place for some time.

→ Roof

Crackings / Material loss

The wooden crossbeams of the wash-house frame show cracks and material loss at the edges of the element.

It is possible that the cracks and material losses observed are due to the natural ageing of the wood and its exposure to the environment. Firstly, the beams have been subjected to the region's climatic hazards. During rainy periods or periods of high humidity, these elements swelled, while during drier periods they shrank. If we consider the life of this building, which should be around 50 - 100 years, it is possible that these climatic variations have had an impact on these beams. It is unlikely that these pathologies are the result of a structural problem. If this were true, repairs would have been carried out long before we intervened, or the cracks would have been more extensive. Finally, it doesn't seem to be a shock either, given the location of the beams and the force required.

As for the loss of material, this is a consequence of the propagation of the cracks. These cracks have weakened the wood, calling into question its cohesion, and causing gaps in the most sensitive areas of the beam, in this case at the edges.

These pathologies are not significant enough to affect the stability of the washhouse roof in the near future. However, we need to keep a close eye on their development, in order to react appropriately if they worsen.

Corrosion

As far as the roof is concerned, we note that most of the metal elements are corroded, whether the fastenings or the post at the entrance to the washhouse. The metal post at the bottom has lost some of its material. It has also had a metal cladding installed, which is also completely corroded.

We were able to observe this phenomenon in the washhouse, at the level of the screws fixed into the wall. All the metal elements of the roof have had to deal with the same problems. They have been subjected to a lot of rain, as well as constant exposure to an atmosphere containing agents harmful to metals, all of which has led to corrosion of these materials. Moreover, this corrosion has been going on for some time, as can be seen from the evolution of the lower part of the post at the entrance to the washhouse. The post has lost material, as if it had been "eaten away". What's more, a metal coating has been affixed to the post, no doubt to protect it from corrosion. However, this protection is also completely corroded. This shows that the phenomenon has been spreading throughout the building for some time.

This alteration can be dangerous, as it affects the mechanical strength of the elements it affects, bearing in mind that these are fasteners and a post, parts required to hold the roof in place. This disorder needs to be monitored and treated to prevent it from worsening, and other elements from being completely "eaten away", risking the collapse of the roof as a result of a deficiency in the load-bearing system.

Soiling / Biological colonization

As in the case of the facings and curbs, the tiles on the washhouse roof show a high concentration of fouling and biological colonization.

Since we're still in the same environment in the Rue des Ferrets, the origins of these exogenous deposits will potentially be the same as those measured on the other structural elements affected by these phenomena.

It would be interesting to monitor the evolution of the tiles. They could become brittle and burst with the addition of salts and/or water due to exogenous deposits. This would prevent the building from remaining watertight.

Graffiti

Graffiti can be seen in several places on the underside of the roof, in line with the beams or chipboard panels. While this does not affect the structure of the building, it does affect its aesthetic appeal. In order to limit the spread of this phenomenon, which could damage the clarity of the washhouse, it would be advisable to monitor their spread and, why not, cover them up.

c. Lavoir rue de l'Eglise

→ Walls

Crackings

On the whole of the building, the rendering is not subject to major deterioration. Nevertheless, cracks are present. They can be seen at the top of the bay and at the bottom of the corner of the wall on the side of the access staircase.

In contrast to the Férets wash house, the rendering is beige in color, with a heavier load of gravel. However, the latter is also made of cement, so the possible causes of this type of pathology are still relevant: freeze-thaw, presence of expansive and/or soluble salts, cement-brick interface, etc.

The deterioration has not spread to the entire washhouse, and therefore does not represent a risk to the durability of the building's facings.

Soiling

Most of the washhouse facings are clean. However, there is a slight amount of soiling on the exterior façade facing the street.

No biological colonies can be seen on this façade. This soiling may be due to dust that has clung to the plaster and spread over it by rain. It may also be due to atmospheric pollution. As mentioned above, this façade runs parallel to a very busy road in the village. The accumulation of motorized traffic in the vicinity could therefore be the cause of the soiling.

At the time of the sanitary inspection, the wall was not affected by the agglomeration of this deterioration. We found no cracks, disintegration, or other signs. For the time being, this phenomenon is only a nuisance from an aesthetic point of view. However, it would be interesting to monitor the evolution of this pathology as road use increases.

Material loss

The lower part of the façade on the town hall side shows a loss of material.

This loss of material may be the result of successive cracks in the plaster at this level. However, given the size and location of the missing piece, as well as the state of the facing on the entire washhouse, this may have been the result of a collision or mechanical action.

This loss of material in no way calls into question the strength of the frame, and therefore does not require any particular attention.

Ragging

On this wash-house, we note the application of a plaster similar to that on the facing concerned, both inside and out. On the other hand, the finish attributed to this layer is different from that observed on the wall in question. That's why we think it's called a levelling coat.

Based on the difference in finish we've observed, we assume that it's patching. There are two ways in which this can be achieved. Firstly, these layers of rendering were applied to repair any disintegration of the original rendering at the ridge purlin. Secondly, this patching may be the result of a 2-stage wall assembly. The builders were able to install the first wall height, taking care to apply the rendering we see today. They then raised the wall to incorporate the ridge purlin for the roof structure. It was then necessary to cover this beam with the same rendering as the first height, to ensure continuity.

On the outside of the washhouse, we note that the rendering is cracking. This indicates a lack of adhesion with the original rendering and facing, which is also possible on the interior façade. One of the main risks of this application is that it no longer attaches to the facing, which could lead to its disintegration and material losses.

→ Bond edges

Crackings

Multiple cracks are present on the concrete edges of the washhouse.

We are facing the same problem as we found on the concrete kerbs of the Féréts washhouse. These elements are both made of the same material and are subject to the same conditions (direct exposure to the atmosphere, contact with water, etc.). Consequently, the possible causes of this deterioration remain identical.

These pathologies could evolve and cause the edges to burst. This would present a risk for all visitors, making the building unsuitable for receiving visitors. What's more, the concrete would become even more exposed, and its condition would deteriorate more rapidly.

Bursting

Bursting is visible on the edges affected by the cracks described above.

As we have already discussed, this pathology occurs in the continuity of the cracks. Thus, the possible causes of the cracks are probably the same that led to the concrete bursting.

In the first instance, these spalls are a safety hazard within the washhouse. These spalls create a lack of grip at the edges, which could destabilize or injure a visitor. Secondly, the concrete no longer has any protection, and is directly exposed to the atmosphere, which will accelerate its deterioration.

Biological colonization

Biological colonization can be observed in the contact zones between the concrete edges and the watercourse.

Bacteria similar to moss or lichen can attach themselves to the material via the wind. However, this phenomenon is also possible via water. In fact, the watercourse running through the village of Montalet-le-Bois is supposed to contain a high concentration of organisms capable of producing fungi and the like. What's more, none of the other elements of the washhouse were affected by the appearance of biological colonies, proving that this alteration is highly localized.

Ragging

Most of the kerbstones are made of grey concrete. However, on the kerb in the direction of the town hall, part of the kerb is made of pink concrete.

We note that these kerbs have numerous cracks and splinters, showing that the concrete is very weathered. Moreover, given the extent of these pathologies, as well as the presence of biological colonies on the patching, this application must be dated. Finally, the concretes come from two different construction campaigns, given their divergent shades. We therefore assume that this is a repair due to excessive bursting.

→ Floor

Cracking

We note the existence of cracks on the floor of the town hall washhouse. These are most noticeable at the entrance to the washhouse, at the level of the access staircase.

The discovery of this alteration is reminiscent of what we said about the slab at the Fêrets wash house. Both the slab at the previous washhouse and the one at this washhouse are made of concrete and are subject to the same environmental and atmospheric conditions. As a result, the cracks we observe are likely to have the same origins: presence of soluble salts (soil, atmospheric pollution, fertilizers, etc.), presence of expansive salts (secondary ettringite, etc.), lack of expansion joints, plant growth.

The fact that the slab of the town hall washhouse has been affected poses a problem in terms of site safety. If the situation worsens, the slab may lose its cohesion, certain areas may lift or burst, and there is a risk of falls and injuries.

Vegetation

Vegetation can be observed in some places inside cracks.

This phenomenon has also been observed at the Féréts washhouse. It is highly probable that these washhouses were built at the same time, so it is possible that the same mistake was made when the slab was laid. The appearance of vegetation shows that no waterproofing was installed between the concrete support and the topsoil.

This pathology represents a major risk in terms of concrete degradation. The topsoil can bring moisture and salts that are harmful to the material. In addition, the pushing force exerted by the plants and their slippery surface during rainy episodes increase the risk of falling into the washhouse.

→ Roof

Exogenic deposit

We note that the roof of the town hall washhouse has numerous exogenous deposits. These deposits are of different natures. We're going to find biological colonies such as mosses or lichens that are spread over a large proportion of the tiles. Subsequently, we also note the presence of other pieces of tile or stone.

As far as biological colonization on the roof is concerned, this developed as a result of several factors. Firstly, the bacteria identified were most likely deposited on the tiles by the wind. Secondly, the rain allowed these colonies to grow and spread over a large part of the roof. As for the pieces of tile and stone, given their size and weight, there are probably two possible explanations. On the one hand, several strong winds could have moved these materials, tearing them from their original position. On the other hand, these pieces may have been deliberately thrown onto the roof of the washhouse.

The growth of biological colonies has a major impact on the organization of the roof and the tiles themselves. Like all organisms, these bacteria seek out empty spaces. This is why, in certain areas of the roof, these colonies are visible between two tiles, and even underneath them. These places occupied by biological colonies lift the tiles, disrupting them and undermining the roof's cohesion. Indeed, if we no longer have this homogeneity, this installation no longer protects the washhouse from water. As for the impact these colonies can have on the tiles, this is due to the bacteria's ability to store water. These organisms are able to capture moisture, water and salts from the atmosphere. All these stored elements can weaken the tiles, making them highly porous and easily cracked. Once again, this questions the roof's ability to keep the building out of water. Regarding the pieces of tile and stone found, this shatters the tiles and causes real mechanical impact when they hit. As with biological colonization, this deteriorates the material itself, as well as the organization of the roof, which means that this installation can no longer ensure the maximum waterproofing of the washhouse.

Cracked tiles

Several tiles have cracked on the roof of the town hall washhouse.

The cracking shows that the tiles have been severely weakened and have lost their mechanical strength. Firstly, there is the possibility of the presence of soluble salts in the atmosphere of Montalet-le-Bois. As we mentioned earlier, there are several potential sources of soluble salts in the area, so it's likely that tiles are affected. Given that tiles are directly affected by rain, which may be laden with these salts, this could further deteriorate these materials. As far as the other possible causes of tile cracking are concerned, we mentioned them in the section on "Exogenous deposits", namely biological colonies and pieces of material.

The appearance of cracks on tiles renders them totally unusable, and they are no longer able to fulfill their role. In other words, they no longer redirect or retain water during rainy episodes. The wash house is no longer completely out of water.

Missing tiles

Looking at the roof, we can see that there are several areas lacking tiles. Firstly, towards the lower part of the roof, we can see that rows of tiles are missing. However, we notice the same phenomenon in the upper part of the roof.

This loss of tiles is the result of a loss of cohesion within the roof, with the tiles falling apart. This defiance is potentially due to the material itself. For example, by being exposed to salts, as mentioned above, the tile can become brittle, crack and the roof deformed. This pathology may also be the result of the spread of biological colonies. As these colonies grow, they seek out empty spaces, which can lead to the tiles lifting off the roof, removing any hold they may have. In addition, certain shocks caused by foreign objects colliding with the roof can cause tiles to fall off. Finally, the vagaries of the weather can also cause many tiles to give way, particularly in the case of high winds.

First and foremost, this alteration poses a problem for the roof's durability. With gaps in the roof, the system is no longer able to fully retain the rain. Subsequently, the fall of several tiles indicates instability within the roof. The risk of an accident should a tile fall on a visitor cannot be ruled out.

Bitumen paper tear

On the reverse side of the tiles, we can see that bitumen paper has been laid, and this appears to be very deteriorated throughout the washhouse. Moisture stains are predominant.

These tears may be due to two factors. Firstly, given the state of the roof, it's not keeping the washhouse completely out of water. Water has therefore reached the bitumen paper, which has become damp, causing it to give way. Secondly, these tears are potentially deliberate. It's possible that someone has intentionally torn certain areas of the installation.

The impact of this will be directly linked to keeping the washhouse out of the water. If we combine the condition of some of the bitumen paper with that of the roof, during heavy rainfall the wash house will be prone to water.

d. Hydraulic mill wheel

We focused on the wheel. The rest of the mill building is maintained and used by the town council.

Loss of material

We note that some wooden parts of the wheel are missing.

Because of its location, the wood is constantly exposed to humidity, and particularly water. The wheel's immobility accelerates the deterioration of the structure. In fact, the same wooden elements are repeatedly subjected to the action of water and humidity without being able to escape. As far as material loss is concerned, this is probably due to rotting and/or temperature variations in the wood. Initially,

wood exposed to water will develop fungi, causing the material to rot and lose its mechanical strength and cohesion. As a result, the wooden element affected by this phenomenon will unhook from the structure to which it is attached. Secondly, if the temperature suddenly rises or falls to cause frost, this can lead to the appearance of large cracks in the wood. Over time, these cracks jeopardize the material's durability.

For the time being, this deterioration has no real impact, as it only affects the non-structural wooden elements of the wheel, bearing in mind that the installation is not in use. However, it is important to monitor the evolution of this deterioration to ensure that it does not affect the structure of the wheel and cause it to fail.

Biological colonization

Biological colonies are visible on the mill wheel in areas in contact with the water. These include mosses, lichens and algae.

It is possible that bacteria that later form biological colonies have attached themselves to the wheel via the wind or the watercourse. Subsequently, this creek allows these organisms to develop. The fact that the same areas of the wheel are in contact with the water, and the lack of movement of the latter, favors the attachment of these colonies to the wheel.

A huge biological colonization has developed on the wheel. We need to be vigilant about the impact this may have on the wood. These organisms can bring moisture, store water and other substances harmful to the material, which can then rot the wood until it fails.

Corrosion of metal elements

We note the presence of a metal bar at the wheel axle, fixed in a metal element to hold the installation in place. In addition, other fasteners such as bolts are visible throughout the wheel frame. All of the above are corroded.

Corrosion has affected all these components, since they are subject to all the conditions required for this phenomenon to develop. In fact, the fasteners are all in the open air and in contact with water, which causes them to corrode.

This deterioration can be dangerous if it worsens. It can cause the affected elements to lose material, reducing their mechanical strength. Subsequently, if these fasteners lose their strength, the wheel itself may be compromised.

PRESERVATION AND ENHANCEMENT PROJECT

1. Preservation and restoration of structural elements

a. Laboratory tests

Following the findings of the sanitary condition tests, analyses will be carried out in order to provide the best possible response to the problems encountered.

These laboratory tests will be used to characterize the materials used. This step is unavoidable if the materials need to be replaced or repaired. This procedure helps to avoid probable incompatibilities between materials. These tests involve observations using a binocular magnifying glass, a scanning electron microscope or X-rays to determine their composition. They can be continued by setting up protocols to test their own properties: porosity, compressive strength, binder dosages, etc.

In addition, the analyses may help to reveal as well as confirm hypotheses concerning the pathologies affecting the washhouses. This approach enables us to target the most appropriate treatments and precautions to be taken in terms of construction, without aggravating the situation. Laboratories working in this field will be able to organize soluble salt assays and use scanning electron microscope observations to identify any anomalies and/or other processes that may help to advance the subject.

In conclusion, laboratory tests function as a complement to the sanitary condition report and are essential to the study we are carrying out in order to gain a better understanding of the adjustments that need to be made. In the context of our project, we are not able to provide results or even tests. Consequently, the recommendations presented below are based solely on observations made beforehand.

b. Consolidation of the actual infrastructures

For the restoration of the infrastructures, we have been working on, which will be included and linked in our enhancement project, we started from our findings in the sanitary diagnosis. We chose to restore the existing elements according to their current state. So, their concrete and cement structure which is not the original one and may not seem very aesthetic or representative of the lifestyles these infrastructures once supported, we feel it is the aim of our project that these systems be shown in their working order. We have tried to take safety into account as much as possible.

Salts

Elements with a cementitious matrix are subject to the action of harmful soluble salts. These can come from a variety of sources: atmospheric pollution, fertilizers, soil, etc. As we have seen, the crystallization of salts can give rise to numerous complications, resulting in a loss of cohesion within the material.

It is therefore necessary to undertake a desalination campaign on all substrates subjected to salts. Initially, for elements that will not be repaired, this process will enable them to endure and annihilate all types of salt development. In the second phase, for surfaces that have been sealed, this campaign will prevent salts from stopping to proliferate within the original material and spreading towards the repair. If this happens at the level of the patching, it will become obsolete, so it must be avoided.

To carry out this desalination campaign, the appropriate compresses need to be selected by a specialist design office. First, these compresses will have to be chosen according to the type of salts identified and the element targeted. Secondly, tests must be carried out to ensure that the chosen solutions do not damage the material, by causing loss of material or granular disintegration when the compress is removed.

Exogenic deposit

Two types of exogenous deposits were noted during the sanitary inspection: biological colonies (moss, algae, etc.) and fouling.

It is essential to remove these phenomena. As far as exogenous deposits are concerned, they bring in water as well as any agents that may be harmful to the materials they come into contact with. As for fouling, as it crystallizes, it can also pick up substances harmful to the materials to which it has adhered. What's more, if the fouling crust is sufficiently dense, it can block exchanges between the exterior and the material, further degrading it. Since we're taking a restoration/conservation approach, it's important to do everything possible to maintain the washes for as long as possible, which means eliminating these exogenous deposits.

To address this problem, trials will need to be carried out to establish the best solution. This could take the form of a compress, a liquid solution, a laser or other means.

First, each type of deposit will be studied separately, since they are not of the same nature. It is highly likely that the solution will diverge between biological colonies and fouling. What's more, even within biological colonies, responses may differ according to the type of organism identified. Subsequently, to select the most appropriate process, tests will have to be carried out. It is important to ensure that the chosen method does not alter the material on which these exogenous deposits are based. This is because the substrate must not be exposed to substances that are incompatible with its composition, or to granular or other disaggregation. A laboratory or design office will then have the task of finding a process that addresses the problem of exogenous deposits while sparing the target substrate.

Claddings

In the various washhouses, cracks and loss of material were visible in the plasterwork. In order to preserve these structures, it is necessary to repair these alterations.

Leaving openings in the materials, such as cracks and splinters, exposes them directly to the stresses of the atmosphere. Unprotected, it will suffer from the vagaries of the weather, soluble salts or any of the other degradations mentioned above. This could accelerate degradation. By sealing off these phenomena, we can limit the need for more extensive repairs later, as well as potential risks such as plaster falling on visitors.

In order to carry out the repairs in the best possible conditions, it will be necessary to characterize the materials. This involves determining the composition of the renderings to be renovated, to ensure that the restoration is compatible with the original. These tests, which are usually carried out in the laboratory, enable us to obtain solutions with a constitution identical to that of the materials studied. As a result, repairs are durable and effective.

First, the sealing stage must follow a campaign of desalination and cleaning of exogenous deposits on the substrate concerned. These prior tasks are mandatory, otherwise plaster renovation will be pointless and repairs will be subject to the same problems as the material to which they adhere. Then, depending on the type of pathology encountered, the filling formulation will not be the same for the sake of workability, accessibility, and adhesion to the substrate. As far as cracks are concerned, the most suitable formulation would be a grout. Given the small size of the cracks in the wash plaster, this solution would allow deep penetration while consolidating the whole. In terms of material loss and splintering, a mortar would be the appropriate procedure. The consistency of the mortar will match that of the existing rendering, facilitating cohesion between the repair, the original and the substrate. However, if the granular disintegration of the substrate is active, the use of a consolidant is essential.

Corroded fixings

During the diagnostic, we noticed that most of the metal elements, whether fasteners or posts, were corroded.

Firstly, as mentioned in the study of the Féréts washhouse, there are some corroded metal fixings which are no longer in use. These are installed in a facing, probably to house planters or other fixtures. When metal corrodes, it tends to increase in volume. This can lead to cracking of the plaster to which these elements are attached. To preserve the aesthetics of the site, and avoid the need for repairs, it's a good idea to remove them. Following removal, the existing plaster will have to be filled in.

If any corroded fasteners are to be retained, they will be treated with a rust inhibitor and repainted in a dark shade or replaced with a rustproof material.

Secondly, we noticed that many metal parts were corroded on the wash-house frames and on the mill wheel. We face a problem while the corrosion affects them not only impairs their mechanical strength, but also causes material losses. As a result, there is a structural risk in maintaining these elements in poor condition, which is likely to cause an accident. They need to be replaced as soon as possible to avoid any problems. Subsequently, it would be advisable to treat the elements against corrosion, by painting or other means. The state of preservation of this protection will need to be monitored to determine when it should be renewed to always keep the new metal elements corrosion-free.

Slabs

Concrete slabs have been installed in the Féréts and rue de l'Eglise washhouses. Unfortunately, as we noted during the health survey, these slabs are in poor condition. There is a proliferation of efflorescence, cracks, and wild vegetation. Given these pathologies, it would be appropriate to replace these elements. If we leave the slabs in their current state, the damage will get worse. Salts are already present inside the material, and will continue to develop, creating new cracks, enlarging existing ones and even causing them

to burst. In addition, wild vegetation may bring other substances that are harmful to concrete and exert a force on slabs that can also cause cracking. This aggravation would call into question the cohesion of the slab and could cause visitors to fall, so it's important to replace them.

On the other hand, other types of landscaped flooring can be used, such as gravel, cobblestones, or others. The first preparation steps are the same as for the concrete slab. The topsoil must be removed, and a geotextile laid. The chosen layout can then be installed. However, we don't want to change the look of the current washhouses, which are part of the commune's heritage, so we're leaning towards a new concrete slab.

On the other hand, it is possible to install a concrete slab. First, the existing slab will have to be dug up. The loose soil can then be levelled, and any problematic wild vegetation removed. The topsoil will then be sealed with a geotextile. Finally, a concrete slab can be poured, with formwork installed beforehand. The composition of the slab should be chosen according to the problems it is intended to solve. It's also important to build expansion joints into the slab to prevent premature cracking or splintering.

On the other hand, other types of engineered flooring can be used: gravel, cobblestones, or others. The first preparation steps are the same as for a concrete slab. The topsoil must be removed, and a geotextile laid. The chosen layout can then be installed.

Bond edges

During our health survey, we observed that the edges of the washes were affected by several pathologies: cracks, loss of material, efflorescence. We can't afford to leave the borders in their current state. Indeed, if we do so, these elements will tend to burst and suffer ever-increasing material loss. To ensure that they can continue to fulfil their role of ensuring the safety of the site and keeping the water in the pools, we need to look for an option to renovate and replace them.

On the one hand, we can renovate these borders. This will involve desalting these elements to combat the salts present within the material. Then, to solve the problem of cracks and material loss, we'll need to fill in the cracks. The concrete used in the kerbstones will be characterized beforehand to ensure that the repairs are maintained and that they are compatible with the existing material. To combat cracks, we'll use a grout formulation, and for material loss, a mortar formulation with prior consolidation if the pathology is still active. These different formulations are designed to respond to the issues they face, depending on the pathology, such as accessibility and maintenance.

On the other hand, instead of undertaking major repairs, the kerbs could be completely replaced. This will be expensive, but it will enable us to eradicate all the pathologies encountered and create kerbs with the same concrete, which will add harmony to the area. Stone kerbs could also be considered. But we don't want to change the aesthetics of the laundries to maintain the history of these places, so we prefer to use concrete.

First, the existing basins will have to be emptied to destroy the existing borders. Then, to avoid salts coming from the soil, we'll install a geotextile. Next, the concrete will be chosen according to the environment of Montalet-le-Bois and the forces it has to store. Formwork will then be prepared, and the concrete poured.

Roof

In the case of the Férets and Rue de l'Eglise washhouses, the roofs are affected by a few problems that need to be resolved.

On the Férets washhouse, the roof is affected by numerous biological colonies, while the beams are subject to cracking and graffiti. For the tiles, we'll need to undertake a cleaning campaign to remove all exogenous deposits. The product used for this task must not be harmful to the tiles in place, and studies must be carried out beforehand. Subsequently, if any tiles are identified as cracked or broken, they will have to be replaced by the same type, small red Vexin tiles. In the case of the beams, the cracks are due to climatic hazards and exposure to the open air, but they do not present a structural risk at present. Studies will have to be carried out to determine whether it is necessary to replace the wooden beams affected by these pathologies. As for the graffiti, it will have to be removed. This can be done by painting them to match the wood color of the beams, or by removing them with a product that is obviously harmless to wood.

As for the rue de l'Eglise washhouse, the roof has broken and cracked tiles, we've also noted the presence of biological colonies and other exogenous deposits, and the bitumen paper is in poor condition. In the case of tiles, we start by removing exogenous deposits (stones, pieces of tile) from the roof, followed by the cleaning of dirt and biological colonies. As with the Férets washhouse, the cleaning product used must be effective against the organisms it encounters, but also harmless to the clay of the tiles. Subsequently, any cracked, broken or lifted tiles will be replaced by the same type already in place, small red Vexin tiles. Subsequently, the bitumen paper is subject to humidity and is torn in certain places, which means it can no longer keep the wash house out of water, so it must be replaced. To do this, the tiles will have to be completely removed. The bitumen paper could then be replaced by chipboard panels, as in the Férets washhouse. Indeed, the panels at Les Férets are still in good condition, which supports the choice of this installation.

2. Enhancement project

In parallel with the planned restoration of the buildings, we're proposing a multi-pronged enhancement project, ideas for which involve various players in the village, as well as regional bodies such as the PNR. While Montalet-le-Bois' water-related heritage is interesting, the village lacks the infrastructure and facilities to attract and welcome visitors. These facilities have yet to be put in place and are already being considered by the town council. Here, we detail our proposals for an educational trail, renewable energies and urban developments that would serve the project.

a. **Promoting water-related heritage: a water trail**

The first important step in promoting our washhouses and mills, Montalet-le-Bois' small-scale heritage, was to integrate them into an itinerary based on the theme of water in the village. This trail would showcase Montalet-le-Bois' hydraulic heritage, following snippets of canals and streams. The aim is for the trail to tell the story of the use of water resources, but also to incorporate elements of biodiversity; the flora and fauna that inhabit the freshwater streams of the Vexin.

With this idea in mind, we contacted the PNR, which already offers a selection of themed trails focusing on the heritage and flora and fauna of the Vexin. They presented us with their development plan, which includes heritage trails. These are unmarked trails crossing one or more rural communes, with itineraries based on information points and *RandoFiches*. All the routes proposed by the PNR can be downloaded from the PNR website.

Our idea therefore fits in with the project already run by the PNR, and we would like to create a *Randofiche* specific to the commune of Montalet-le-Bois. The trail would be a 2.5km loop with several vertical drops, with the lavoirs and mill as points of interest. The trail would start at the lavoir de la source, at the source of the Bernon, where a parking lot would be provided. As the trail is short and doesn't follow the Bernon through the whole commune, we'd like to propose an extension to the trail that would go past the washhouse on the main road to the hamlet of Damply and the Moulin des Prés, and why not to the mill located downstream of the Bernon in the commune of Jambville.

We can also link this trail to the short hiking circuit that runs around the communes bordering Montalet-le-Bois and imagine day hikes.

PR trail (small scale hikes), IGN map – Source : Geoportail.gouv.fr

We're looking to provide mediation on the history and lifestyles of the French Vexin. To this end, we think that the *Randofiche* could be complemented by audio terminals with testimonials from Montalet-le-Bois' inhabitants. Some families have lived in the village for a very long time, and hearing anecdotes from the commune's elders could make this local history much livelier and accessible. These recordings can be supported by explanatory images from the personal archives of residents. What's more, subtitles could be used to make the animation accessible to all, including the hearing-impaired.

The entire hiking trail is already laid out and used by residents. Several sections are already surfaced in a way that is suitable for walking and for disabled people, such as compacted earth paths in the fields, or asphalt paths as some sections pass through the town using the sidewalks. As a result, there will be minimal development work required. However, to ensure that these paths are accessible to all, certain features will need to be checked. Certain areas will have to be cleared of undergrowth and weeds, and some slopes may have to be modified. The entire route will have a minimum width of 1.40 m and maximum gradients of 5% to ensure access for PRMs.

During our telephone conversations with PNR du Vexin officials, we were informed that a project to create a heritage trail is underway with the commune of Montalet-le-Bois for 2024. The trail project alone will be 70% financed by the PNR, with a budget of €15,000 for the layout and installation of the panels.

The PNR is also interested in integrating our research into this future trail.

b. Reusing water to generate electricity; restoring the mill wheel

As part of an initiative to upgrade the town of Montalet-le-Bois and after several discussions with the town council, we're hoping to get the mill wheel up and running again.

Not only to restore the old mechanism, but also to give it and the watercourse a new use. The hydraulic system, which has been in place for centuries, will be reused in this project as part of an energy recovery process. So, what has been chosen is to replace the current wheel at the town hall, which is not only blocked but also corroded and broken, with a new wheel linked to a generator. The idea is to retain a traditional exterior while using water energy to generate electricity via a mechanism inside the building.

The structures around the wheel would be cleaned and treated against biological colonization.

Actual wheel in place, personal photography, February 2023

In order to dimension the replacement installation, a process to determine the energy input provided by the wheel and the various components to be added will therefore be carried out, to finally conclude on the validity of this aspect of the Montalet-le-Bois project.

As previously mentioned, the current mill wheel has been completely shut down, due to deterioration caused by lack of maintenance and since the mill stopped working, whether from an energy point of view or from the town's point of view.

Fortunately, the design of the current wheel, which is installed over the water inlet, is the most efficient paddle wheel system. There are several types:

The "over-the-top" installation: the one we have in the case of the Montalet-le-Bois waterwheel. This is the most efficient of the waterwheel systems usually used in mills. The water inflow above the wheel fills the troughs, creating forward rotation while maintaining the same kinetic potential. The weight of the water thus provides the power.

Mechanism of the « over-the-top » installation

The "from below" installation, which is the opposite of Montalet-le-Bois' system, is the least energy-efficient. With the water inlet located below the wheel, kinetic energy losses would appear to be zero, but the exact opposite is true, as the wheels receive less force for rotation.

The "à poitrine" wheel system, halfway between the two previous systems, both in terms of design and energy input, provides a "side" water supply, filling several troughs simultaneously.

Mechanism of the « from below » installation

Mechanism of the « à poitrine » installation

Therefore, the system already in place at Montalet-le-Bois already provides the most optimal conditions thanks to the type of installation we have on the town hall wheel.

This will enable us to determine that even if the energy input is not enormous on the scale of the city, it will be profitable because we have a system with low energy losses.

To convert the kinetic energy created by the wheel's rotational movement into electrical energy that can then be used directly on the grid, a permanent magnet generator must be installed. This is a system that, by rotating a magnet directly connected to the wheel inside a coil, creates an alternating electric current that can then be used directly, without the need to invest in a current conversion device.

The advantages of using a permanent magnet generator include:

- No need for a current converter, which reduces the cost of the installation.
- Ease of installation and operation, since only one component needs to be installed.
- The kinetics of the wheel system are the most optimal of all watermill systems, allowing the full potential of the permanent-magnet generator to be exploited, since there is little loss of mechanical energy.

There are several generator ranges associated with a different power output range, each with a different rated speed:

	<u>145 ATK</u>	<u>190 ATK</u>	<u>300 ATK</u>	<u>400 ATK</u>	<u>500 ATK</u>	<u>800 ATK</u>
Puissance :	200 W à 5,5 kW	1,1 kW à 8,5 kW	3 kW à 19 kW	4 kW à 33 kW	4,7 kW à 43 kW	7 kW à 99 kW
Vitesse nominale :	650 tr/min à 1500 tr/min	500 tr/min à 1500 tr/min	tr/min à 800 tr/min	220 tr/min à 800 tr/min	150 trs / min à 600 trs / min	80 tr/min à 400 tr/min

The permanent magnet turbine chosen is the 300 ATK, as it doesn't require a minimum number of revolutions per minute, enabling continuous power generation.

It costs around €2,300, and installation is around €600.

300 ATK magnet turbine

Projects involving the installation of renewable energy production systems are not subsidized by the PNR, but the commune can benefit from investment subsidies, starting with the *Contrat Rural* (Region + Département), which can help up to 70% of a maximum of €300,000 worth of work.

This installation would generate a small electrical current. A project that would highlight the role of water in the village rather than contributing to the commune's electricity supply.

c. Urban development

Parking

The major constraint in Montalet-le-Bois is the lack of parking spaces. The current layout is intended only for village residents. During our visit, we saw that there is no parking in the center or outside the village. If we want to attract visitors to Montalet-le-Bois, we need to create a parking infrastructure.

We would like to build a parking lot near the Bernon spring at the spring washhouse, which is located on plot 188 slightly outside the village center. We're also planning to build this facility on parcel 260, which is a *zone d'agriculture protégée* (valorized agricultural zone) with a surface area of around 4.52 ha. It is possible that this land is privately owned, so we'll have to consider buying it back. Our aim is to create a facility that can accommodate twenty vehicles, to welcome visitors and hikers.

Finally, we are basing the design and dimensions of the parking lot on the Grand Paris Seine & Oise intercommunal PLU.

Plot n.o.260 on the plan cadastral, Source : cadastre.data.gouv.fr

When building the parking lot, we'll consider the commune's policy and the regulations in force for this type of development.

The parking lot can be made of concrete, topsoil, gravel, grassed slabs filled with minerals or other materials. For Montalet-le-Bois and the PLUi, conservation of the natural Vexin landscape is paramount, so we have applied this vision to our installation.

It is therefore not an option to use concrete for this layout, as it will not allow water to infiltrate the salt, and risks of soil pollution are to be expected. In fact, we prefer to install a totally natural, permeable surface, which is why we chose grass-covered slabs for the parking spaces. This choice seems appropriate to us, since car traffic on natural ground such as bare topsoil or gravel will leave visible traces, especially in maneuvering areas.

After a great deal of research, and to model the project as accurately as possible, we relied on the documentation provided by ECOVEGETAL. First, before starting work, bearing capacity studies will have to be carried out on the subgrade to see if the parking lot is feasible. If the subgrade meets bearing capacity criteria, it will be excavated to a depth of 30 to 75 cm, compacted and a geotextile installed. A range of materials will then be used before the slabs are laid:

10 to 40 cm: load-bearing, draining material with a diameter of 40/80 mm.

20 cm: a mixture of 65% to 70% concrete crushed stone or 30/60 pozzolan and 30% to 35% HYDROFERTIL. HYDROFERTIL is a substrate made from ECOVEGETAL's own soil, ensuring a minimum 25% water retention to feed the future lawn.

4 cm: FERTILIT is an ECOVEGETAL product containing baked earth, pozzolan and compost with a grain size of 0/15 mm. This layer ensures effective water retention and drainage.

Each layer is compacted to optimize the mechanical performance of the parking lot. In addition, calculations carried out by the company will determine whether a drain should be installed. However, every effort will be made to ensure that the materials store all future rainwater underground, and their thickness will be calculated accordingly.

Once the ground has been prepared, the ECORASTER E50 slabs can be laid. These slabs, measuring 1.33 m² and 5 cm in height, are made of 100% recycled polyethylene with mortise-and-tenon fastening systems. Pre-grassed slabs can be ordered for immediate planting. During installation, care should be taken to position the cut tiles at the edges of the landscaped areas, and to keep the whole modules in the most stressed areas. Once the slabs are in place, a cylinder is run over them. To delimit the squares, protruding studs will be used, which fit into the cells of the slabs. They will be placed every 20 cm, making around 12 studs per marking.

Finally, the upkeep of the grassed paving stones is very important. They need to be watered after installation, and they need to take root before the parking lot can be opened to the public. Fertilizers can then be recommended at different times of the year to help the grass develop. As far as mowing is concerned, this should be carried out by cars without any problem. However, if necessary, it's best to leave 5 cm of grass above the slabs. But these installations are also designed to let nature take its course, and to be as low-maintenance as possible, if that's what the municipality wants.

ECORASTER E50 grassed slabs / Plots de marquage - Source : ecovegetal.com

From now on, we will be concentrating on the layout for the access roads. According to ECOVEGETAL, the strength of grass-covered slabs is not sufficient to fulfill the role of these walkways, so it is preferable to use mineral-filled slabs. As with grass slabs, the subgrade to be used for these installations must be tested to see whether it can withstand the creation of the parking lot. If, following calculations, the subgrade meets expectations, it can be lowered to a depth of 30 to 75 cm. This is followed by compaction and the laying of a geotextile. A succession of different layers will then be laid:

- d. 10 to 40 cm: load-bearing, draining material with a diameter of 40/80 mm.
- e. 20 cm: draining material with continuous grading to ensure good compactness
- f. 3 cm: *mignonnette de seine*, porphyry, pozzolana, quartz, flint and others with a grain size < 10 mm.

Once installed, all layers should be compacted. As with the grass slabs, ECOVEGETAL will carry out calculations to determine the depths required and whether a drain is needed to manage the groundwater stored in the soil. Once the soil has been prepared in such a way as to meet the requirements of the parking lot while remaining permeable, the ECORASTER E50 slabs can be laid. These slabs, measuring 1.33 m² and 5

ECORASTER E50 slabs field up with minerals -
Source : ecovegetal.com

cm in height, are made from 100% recycled polyethylene with mortise-and-tenon fastening systems. For access roads, the slabs will be filled with *mignonnette de seine*, porphyry, pozzolan, quartz, flint and other minerals with a grain size < 10 mm. After filling, the minerals should be vibrated and topped up to the finished level. Afterwards, all these arrangements are compacted with a cylinder. When laying, care should be taken to position the cut slabs around the landscaped areas, and to keep the whole modules in the most stressed areas.

As for the topsoil removed from the parking lot, this could be reused by the commune or for future work on the parking area.

From now on, we will be looking at the rest of the parking lot facilities.

At the entrance and exit to the parking lot, we would like to install 2.10 m-high, 3 m-wide wooden gantries. This will limit access to certain vehicles for which the parking lot may not be large enough. This will also prevent abuse (unauthorized camping, truck parking, etc.).

However, if vehicles taller than 2.10 m need to access the parking lot, the crossbar can be removed. What's more, the gantries will be made of wood, once again demonstrating Montalet-le-Bois' commitment to innovative projects while preserving its rural identity. When they are installed, the posts of the porticoes will have to be sealed. Given that the posts measure 2.80 m, 40 cm of these elements need to be driven in to ensure the porticoes' stability. This will be done directly in the ground. To achieve this, the ground must be made sufficiently compact and stable. Two holes are dug for the posts. A geotextile will then be placed at the bottom of the excavation, followed by a suitable concrete, another geotextile will be positioned, and the soil will be compacted. In addition, to avoid misdirection of traffic in the parking lot in future, "Entrance" and "Exit" signs will be placed on the corresponding gantries.

Wooden gate

Source : normequip.com

Next, in line with the PLUi's commitment to planted fences between new constructions and natural areas, we have chosen to install country hornbeam hedges. These plants should be planted between the end of November and the end of March, avoiding frost, and putting 1m between each plant. The ground must be spaded to prepare it for the hedge. A hole is then made in the ground, and the plant is inserted until its collar is level with the finished soil. Afterwards, a film is laid over the plants, held in place by soil at the ends. The plant mulch is laid on top of this film. This device combats weeds, protects plants from the cold, fertilizes the soil and retains water. Watering should be monitored in the first year to determine whether the hornbeams are lacking water. The important thing is to check that the soil is always moist, so that the plants can develop properly. Pruning is also necessary at the beginning to give the hedge the desired shape. Hedges should be kept to a height of around 1.50 m and a width of around 1 m to ensure that they blend in well with the landscape and do not disrupt the layout of the parking lot. Hedges can also be composed of the following local species: hazelnut, cypress, broom, boxwood, lilac, wild rose, fusain, hawthorn, privet, viburnum, or hornbeam, to the exclusion of exotic species (cedar, cypress).

Finally, signposts will be placed at the places for disabled people.

Hornbeam hedges - Source : lemurvegetal.com

The start of the hike begins at the lavoir de la source on plot 188, which is not close to the parking lot. To solve this problem, a path will be laid in plots 137 and 138 to reach the parking area. However, to reach plot 138 from the parking lot, the road must be crossed. It is therefore necessary to install a crosswalk at the entrance. The layout is based on traditional dimensions, strips 5 m long and 0.5 m wide separated by 0.65 m each. Subsequently, we would like to install speed bumps nearby to ensure pedestrian safety.

Sections de Trafics

Nb véhicules (TMJA)

- 40000 véhicules/jour et plus
- 25000 à 39999 véhicules/jour
- 15000 à 24999 véhicules/jour
- 4500 à 14999 véhicules/jour
- 2500 à 4499 véhicules/jour
- 0 à 2499 véhicules/jour

Daily attendance on the D205 - Source : arcgis.com

According to the ArcGIS Online website, traffic on the D205 through Montalet-le-Bois ranges from 0 to 2,499 vehicles/day, which allows for the installation of speed bumps, since traffic is less than 3,000 vehicles/day in a built-up area. We would like to reduce the speed limit to 30 km/h, and therefore install cushion-type speed bumps in each direction. Their dimensions are 3 m long, 1.80 m wide and 6.5 cm high. These elements are then installed using metal fixings directly embedded in the asphalt. Signs will also be erected to inform pedestrians of the installation. Thanks to these installations, pedestrians will be able to access the footpath in complete safety.

Speed bump type *cousin berlinois* - Source : prozon.comarcgis.com

Then, as the parking lot is developed, the road markings on the departmental road will also have to be changed. We've installed a wooden gantry gate for entry and exit, but cars coming from Montalet-le-Bois can't access the parking lot, so we'll need to set up a mixed line. This mixed line will extend the distance of the parking lot entrance and will be discontinuous on the side coming from the commune.

In this section, we'll look at all the dimensions that will enable us to model the parking lot.

For this parking lot, the traffic lane will be 5 m wide, and the radius of gyration taken into account will be 11 m. The radius value is an average based on all the vehicles likely to use the parking lot. However, the lane near the main road will be 7 m wide, to allow sufficient space for vehicles and pedestrians to circulate safely. In addition, a 1.40 m gap will be left between the parking lot entrance gate and the fence to allow visitors to cross the road.

Parking areas in this type of parking lot are therefore 2.30 m wide, with 10 cm of road markings, and 5 m long. For PRMs, the dimensions change, measuring 3.30 m wide with 10 cm of pavement markings and 5 m in length. In addition, the slope of the parking lot will be 5% to ensure accessibility for all. The slope of the site will be adjusted to meet this requirement when the ground is excavated to lay the mineral-filled grass slabs. It is also at this stage that the layout of the access to the parking lot to connect it to the main road will have to be worked out.

Here, after elaboration and calculation, are the plans for this 21-space parking lot, including 1 space for disabled access. This future development will occupy an area of 886 m² on the plot

Parking implantation

Village's newspaper

The washhouses can also be used to promote the current story of the surrounding area in the form of a gazette, available free of charge in the laundries. It is very important that these leaflets are part of a sustainable development policy. The intention is to create this newspaper using a short circuit and biodegradable materials. What's more, a QR code will be placed next to the bins containing these newspapers so that they can be accessed via a smartphone. This process will help avoid surplus production of this future gazette. Finally, to avoid intensive printing, this magazine could appear only once or twice a month.

Aménagements aux abords des lavoirs

Our aim is to turn the washhouses into places for "tourism" of the local heritage, as well as places for sharing experiences and for living. For this vision to become a reality, these places need to be treated as public spaces, with landscaped surroundings to create an attractive, relaxing, and contemplative setting. These living spaces would also develop a certain attachment to the washhouses.

As far as the Férets wash house is concerned, we have a surface area of around 59 m² available for developing this area to make it attractive. Benches and a table tennis table could be installed. If this is the case, there is no need to carry out any work, just treat the existing grass to make the area more welcoming. The only special care to be taken with the ground will be when laying the concrete foundations for the benches and other installations. To prevent any future damage to the material or contact with the ground, a geotextile will be installed before pouring, and suitable concrete will be used. Subsequently, fencing will have to be put up around the area to prevent any kind of accident, as it is close to a road. To respect Montalet-le-Bois' desire not to alter the landscape, we would like to install wooden fences in pine with vertical, openwork cladding. First of all, we'll need to insert the 14 cm-diameter posts, 2 m high and 1.50 m above ground level. As for their foundation, a hole should be dug for each post and a geotextile placed in it. A suitable concrete will then be poured to a depth of 20 cm. Once the concrete is dry, gravel will be added to a depth of 20 cm to ensure drainage, then covered with topsoil. The posts will be pre-drilled to accommodate two rows of 8 cm diameter rails. Access to this area should be via a gate in the same style as the fence. This would open inwards and be 1.40 m wide. In the future, flowerbeds or other landscaping could be added to nourish this space.

Parcelle aux abords du lavoir des Férets – Source geoportail.gouv.fr

Wooden log fence - Source: blehen.com

Wooden log door - Source: techni-contact.com

Here is an example of what might look like:

Concerning the spring washhouse, it is located close to a large plot of land also belonging to the commune, which is hilly and bordered by a rural road and the Bernon stream below. This area has been left undeveloped.

We believe that this space could be developed into a village-wide meeting place to fill the lack of public space in Montalet-le-Bois that we have observed. Indeed, the village has no central square, café or meeting place. This space could therefore become a place for meetings, exchanges and to celebrate municipal events such as the *fête de la musique*, *fête des voisins* or others near the new parking lot. It would also serve as a reminder of the washhouse's former role as a meeting place for washerwomen. It could also

be a pleasant picnic spot for walkers discovering the Vexin, complementing the space with the picnic table next to the washhouse.

Area to develop– Personal photograph, Mars 2023

Our aim is to design this space so that it blends seamlessly into the landscape. This could take place on plot no. 134, which has a surface area of 6,620 m². To accommodate the public, terraces could be dug into the ground, with a wooden crossbeam acting as a seat. Staircases will also be dug into the ground for access. To prevent falls when the ground is wet, wooden planks can be placed on each step. However, a blank area below the bleachers should be preserved to accommodate a banquet or a stage, depending on the occasion, as this space is intended to host both communal festivities and shows. Indeed, the creation of a place of celebration could also serve to attract people from outside Montalet-le-Bois, who might be keen to get involved in the commune and preserve its heritage.

In total, we estimate that this leisure space will occupy a surface area of around 1060 m².

Plot no. 134, next to the plot no. 188 occupied by the washhouse

Exemple of development: vegetal stairs - Source : larochesuryon.maville.com

In the same vein, we thought it would be interesting to turn the washhouses back into living spaces and use them as support for art and self-expression.

The Féréts washhouse has bare exterior cladding (overlooking the space we could create at the rear), while the Town Hall washhouse has bare interior cladding, but in line with our ambition to make local residents want to use these places again.

The cement appearance of the washhouses means that these surfaces can be covered without damaging the old buildings. Other monuments dating from similar eras, such as the former town hall and school located in the center of the village, further demonstrate the heritage of this era.

We think that the children of the Montalet-le-Bois school group could be integrated into this approach to create a link with their town and its water heritage. Give them their own vision of their town, and take ownership of its infrastructure by creating a fresco, ceramic tiles or similar. We believe that this playful approach can enable teachers to tackle subjects such as ecosystems or the village's heritage with their pupils. It is part of the village dynamic and would draw attention to the lavoirs.

A local artist could also be approached to create a piece. As with the children, the artistic process could take the form of a fresco or mosaic depicting the flora and fauna of the village and surrounding area. The representation of this theme is very important, as it will raise awareness of the need to protect the surrounding ecosystem.

Panneaux photovoltaïques

In line with the energy recovery approach initiated by the washhouses in Montalet-le-Bois, one of the projects we have developed is to equip the wash house in rue de l'Eglise with photovoltaic panels, to power the lights around the town hall in an environmentally friendly way.

There are several types of solar panels available:

Monocrystalline solar panels

These panels are often used for their "all-black" appearance, making them easy to install on any roof. They have a higher efficiency than most other types of solar panels (16-28% of solar energy is converted into electricity), because their crystalline cells are better at converting solar radiation into electrical energy, thanks to the size of their monocrystalline cells, which improve the movement of electrons within them. Although these panels are more suitable for hot regions, and less efficient in cold and temperate regions, this difference is not significant in France, where temperatures are not high enough. However, the cost is higher than for other panels, for the same surface area.

Polycrystalline solar panels

As the name suggests, this type of panel features cells made of several crystals, by fusing silicon. The result is no less qualitative, but as the crystalline structure is more complex than that of monocrystalline photovoltaic panels, the movement of electrons is less important than in the case of monocrystalline solar panels. As a result, polycrystalline solar panels are less efficient (14 to 18% of solar radiation is converted into electrical energy) than monocrystalline ones. However, they are less costly, more environmentally friendly and lose less energy through heat loss.

Amorphous solar panels

This is another type of solar cell, used for small installations or systems. These panels have a very low efficiency (6 to 9% of solar radiation is converted into electrical energy) and are composed of a very thin and sometimes bendable layer of silicon. As a result, they are much less expensive than mono- or polycrystalline solar panels but are not at all on the same level in terms of performance.

Monocrystalline solar panels

polycrystalline solar panels

Amorphous solar panels

In our case, we'd need to install a panel on the roof of one of Montalet-le-Bois' washhouses. This raises several issues, including installation, aesthetics, and maintenance, as well as energy issues such as the energy the panel(s) will produce.

Ideally, and in accordance with UDAP (Departmental unit for architecture and heritage) requirements, the panel(s) should be installed in accordance with the following conditions: In order to preserve the ridge, which is the most visible part of the building in the landscape, solar panels/thermal collectors should be predominantly vertical, with a matt black tint, and installed from one end of the roof to the other in a band at the lower part of the roof.

Theoretical dimensioning (without choice of specific panel):

Knowing that for the washhouse on which the photovoltaic cells are to be installed, we have the following dimensions:

Length: 4.25m

Width: 2.21m

We will assume that only a quarter of the width needs to be covered at the bottom. This gives us an area to cover of 4.25 m by about 55 cm, i.e. approx. 2.35 m².

Then, using the winter and summer sunshine maps of France, we can determine the energy production of a panel per day (under ideal conditions), in summer and winter, using the yield formula.

Location of the solar panels

$$\text{yield} = \frac{\text{Energy used}}{\text{Energy received}} \Leftrightarrow \text{Energy used} = \text{yield} \times \text{Energy received}$$

Multiplying the solar panel's nominal output by the amount of sunshine will tell us how much it will produce per day. For yields, we'll take the values below, which are averages of the maximum and minimum yields of solar panels:

- Monocrystalline: efficiency = 22%.
- Polycrystalline: yield = 16%.
- Amorphous: efficiency = 7.5%.

As for the amount of sunlight captured by the solar cells per day, which corresponds to the energy received in the yield formula, we have the following values:

Winter: 1.09 kWh/m²/day

Summer: 3.83 kWh/m²/day

We can therefore use this data to calculate the energy produced, which corresponds to the energy used in our yield formula, for each of the solar panel types mentioned:

- Monocrystalline :

$$\text{Energy output (winter)} = 1.09 \times 0.22 = 0.2398 = 239.8 \text{ Wh/m}^2/\text{day}$$

$$\text{Energy output (summer)} = 3.83 \times 0.22 = 0.8426 = 842.6 \text{ Wh/m}^2/\text{day}$$

- Polycrystalline :

$$\text{Energy output (winter)} = 1.09 \times 0.16 = 0.1744 = 174.4 \text{ Wh/m}^2/\text{day}$$

$$\text{Energy output (summer)} = 3.83 \times 0.16 = 0.5648 = 564.8 \text{ Wh/m}^2/\text{day}$$

- Amorphous :

$$\text{Energy output (winter)} = 1.09 \times 0.075 = 0.08175 = 81.75 \text{ Wh/m}^2/\text{day}$$

$$\text{Energy output (summer)} = 3.83 \times 0.075 = 0.28725 = 287.25 \text{ Wh/m}^2/\text{day}$$

The monocrystalline panel remains the most efficient, as previously stated.

It will therefore be easier for us to choose this panel to power the lights around the town hall.

Actual dimensions :

As previously stated, the surface area occupied by the photovoltaic cells should not exceed one-quarter of the lower roof area, i.e. no more than $2.35 \text{ m}^2 \pm 10 \text{ cm}$ (the tolerance is set by the UDAP).

We therefore looked for "full black" monocrystalline solar panels, because according to the UDAP they must be black, with the appropriate dimensions. We found the solar panel below: Dimensionnement réel :

Caractéristiques

Puissance max	50W	Coefficient de température (Pm)	-0.43%/°C
Tolérance	0/+3%	Coefficient de température (Voc)	-0.34%/°C
Tension à puissance max (Vmp)	17.8V	Coefficient de température (Icc)	0.05%/°C
Intensité à puissance max (Imp)	2.81A	Dimensions cellule	125 x 62.5mm
Tension à vide (Voc)	22.3V	Nombre de cellules	36
Intensité court-circuit (Isc)	3.03A	Dimensions	640 x 550 x 35mm
Rendement cellule	20.6%	Poids	4.1kg
Rendement module	14.2%		
NOTC/TUC	45+/-2°C		
Température de fonctionnement	-40 à +85°C		

This panel is 64 cm long and 55 cm wide, so it covers 35.2 cm^2 per unit. So, if we line up 7 of them on the washery roof, 2.464 m^2 of surface area will be covered by the panels, which is within our tolerance for the authorized surface area to be covered.

We can then easily determine the amount of electricity we'll produce, using the same formulas as above, bearing in mind that this time there will be 7 panels:

Yield (nominal) = 20.6%; Energy produced (winter) = $0.206 \times 1.09 = 0.224 \text{ kWh/m}^2/\text{day}$
Efficiency (nominal) = 20.6%; Energy output (summer) = $0.206 \times 3.83 = 0.789 \text{ kWh/m}^2/\text{day}$

So for the 7 panels:

Energy output (winter) = $0.224 \times 7 = 1.568 \text{ kWh/m}^2/\text{day}$
Energy produced (summer) = $0.789 \times 7 = 5.523 \text{ kWh/m}^2/\text{day}$

If a streetlight has an output of 500W, and that it operates from 7pm to 1am and between 5am and 8am, that's 10 hours. The energy consumption of the luminaires corresponds to:

Energy consumed = Power (W) \times Time (h) = $500 \times 10 = 5000 = 5 \text{ kWh/day}$

In conclusion, the energy produced by the panels will be more than enough to power a luminaire in summer, but not in winter, so they will be useful in the case of additional energy in both cases.

Installation costs

In addition to the panels, we need an inverter to connect the photovoltaic cells to the city's electricity grid. It will be used to convert the direct current generated by the solar panels into alternating current.

Example of inverter

Modèle	DS3-L	DS3
Données d'entrée (DC)		
Puissance module recommandée (STC) par entrée DC	de 250Wp à 525Wp+	de 300Wp à 660Wp+
Plage de Tension MPPT	25V-55V	32V-55V
Plage de tension de fonctionnement	16V-60V	26V-60V
Tension d'entrée DC maximum	60V	
Courant d'entrée DC maximum	18A x 2	20A x 2
Données de sortie (AC)		
Puissance de sortie maximale	730VA	880VA
Tension de sortie nominale*	230V/184V-253V	
Courant de sortie nominale	3.2A	3.8A
Plage maximale de variation de fréquence*	50Hz/48Hz-51Hz	
Facteur de Puissance (Adjustable)	0.99/0.8 avance...0.8 retard	
Nombre Maximum d'unités par branche de 20A**	6	5
Rendement		
Rendement maximum	97%	
Rendement CEC	96.5%	
Rendement MPPT Nominal	99.5%	
Consommation électrique de nuit	20mW	
Données mécaniques		
Plage de température ambiante de fonctionnement	- 40 °C à + 65 °C	
Plage de température de fonctionnement interne	- 40 °C à + 85 °C	
Dimensions (W x H x D)	262mm x 218mm x 41.2mm	
Poids	2.6kg	
Section du câble de sortie AC	2.5mm ²	
Type de connecteurs	MC4	
Système de refroidissement	Convection - Pas de ventilateur	
Indice de protection	IP67	

We have come up with the model above, specifying that will be using the DS3 model. The inverter's 97% efficiency makes losses in the wires during current conversion negligible.

As for the final cost, add up the cost of the 7 panels and the inverter:

Total cost of photovoltaic system = 7 × cost of one solar panel + cost of inverter

Total cost of photovoltaic system = 7 × 665 + 209 = 4864 euros

The total cost of the system will therefore be 4864 euros.

3. Project costing and implementation

We have based the costing of our project on the work described in the previous sections. In other words, the quantities entered in our costing table are based on the plans we have created, the implementations we have detailed and the installations we have chosen to preserve and enhance the Montalet-le-Bois washhouses.

As for the unit prices we have opted for, they come from various companies in the construction sector or specialized websites. When they define work requiring labor, the prices include both material and installation.

Chiffrage Montalet le bois					
N°	Désignation	Quantité	Unité	P.U	Prix
Étude préalable					
1	Constat d'état sanitaire (avec prélèvements et sondages)	1	U	3 000,00 €	3 000,00 €
2	Analyse laboratoire	1	U	6 000,00 €	6 000,00 €
				TOTAL HT	9 000,00 €
Préconisations					
2	Nettoyage des colonies biologiques	54,63	m ²	25,00 €	1 365,75 €
3	Nettoyage des salissures	63,99	m ²	22,00 €	1 407,78 €
4	Nettoyage toiture	20,97	m ²	27,50 €	576,68 €
5	Campagne de dessalement	81,81	m ²	55,00 €	4 499,55 €
6	Réparation des fissures	8	m ²	58,00 €	464,00 €
7	Réparation de l'enduit	2,5	m ²	81,00 €	202,50 €
8	Réparation de béton (sac de 25 kg)	4	m ²	30,00 €	120,00 €
9	Remplacement de poutre métallique corrodée	2,4	ml	68,00 €	163,20 €
10	Remplacement de poteau métallique corrodée	1,7	ml	33,20 €	56,44 €
11	Réparations tuiles	7,15	m ²	280,00 €	2 002,00 €
12	Mise en place de panneaux en bois agglomérés	8,11	m ²	31,50 €	255,47 €
13	Enlèvement graffitis	2,5	m ²	35,00 €	87,50 €
<i>Dalle béton</i>					
14	Démolition dalle béton	11,89	m ²	30,00 €	356,70 €
15	Évacuation gravats dalle béton	1,78	m ³	40,00 €	71,20 €
16	Pose géotextile	11,89	m ²	1,20 €	14,27 €
17	Coulage béton	11,89	m ²	72,50 €	862,03 €
				TOTAL HT	12 505,05 €
Préservation et valorisation					
<i>Parking</i>					
18	Rachat parcelle	886	m ²	758,00 €	671 588,00 €
19	Terrassement	420,75	m ³	21,00 €	8 835,75 €
20	Chargement et évacuation terre	597,5	m ³	9,00 €	5 377,50 €
21	Dalle ECOVEGETAL GREEN	257	m ²	90,00 €	23 130,00 €
22	Dalle ECOVEGETAL MINERAL	508	m ²	65,00 €	33 020,00 €
23	Plot de marquage	276	U	1,60 €	441,60 €
24	Portique de gabarit en bois	2	U	571,00 €	1 142,00 €
25	Haie de charmes champêtres	138	U	2,00 €	276,00 €
26	Poubelle	2	U	259,00 €	518,00 €
27	Ralentisseur coussin berlinois	2	U	788,00 €	1 576,00 €
28	Marquage au sol	1	U	50,00 €	50,00 €
29	Installation électrique	3	U	1 800,00 €	5 400,00 €
30	Borne sonore	3	U	400,00 €	1 200,00 €
<i>Panneaux photovoltaïques</i>					
31	Pose des panneaux photovoltaïques	7	U	95,00 €	665,00 €
32	Ondulateur	1	U	209,00 €	209,00 €
33	Turbine moulin	1	U	2 900,00 €	2 900,00 €
<i>Aménagement espace des Férrets</i>					
34	Clôture en rondins de bois et lisses	30,1	ml	33,60 €	1 011,36 €
35	Portillon rondins de bois	1	U	592,00 €	592,00 €
36	Banc	5	U	650,00 €	3 250,00 €
37	Table de ping-pong	1	U	1 280,00 €	1 280,00 €
38	Poubelle	1	U	259,00 €	259,00 €
39	Aménagement espace de la source	1160	m ²	38,52 €	44 683,20 €
				TOTAL HT	807 404,41 €
TOTAL HT					828 909,46 €

The costing we have provided only gives the dry disbursements for the work we have planned, which are €828,909.46, including materials, labor and equipment.

In order to obtain the cost price, in other words the real cost of all the expenses involved, this estimate will have to be sent to companies so that they can apply their sales coefficient. This coefficient considers site costs, overheads, profit/loss and contingencies, which the company will calculate. Due to a lack of resources and information, we are unable to determine this figure. Once this coefficient has been calculated, it will be added to the dry disbursements we have obtained. Once we have this information, the actual cost of the work we are planning will be known.

CONCLUSION

We were fortunate to be involved in a project that resonated with the will of a willing municipality to see a project come to life in order to revitalize itself, allowing us to be put in a concrete situation. Our suggestions and biases will be made available to the commune of Montalet-le-Bois and the PNR du Vexin, in the hope that they can be used to support their project.

In this project, the challenge was to successfully promote four different sites while incorporating them into a common idea of hiking. But we also had to find the right balance in a heritage project on the scale of the village, so that it didn't become invasive. We tried to avoid an overly urban and touristy vision for this small village, so as not to denature it. We tried to think of a project that would meet the expectations of the commune, focused on the well-being of its inhabitants and its dynamism, while remaining in keeping with the rural character of the Vexin Français. The project was therefore designed to serve both the leisure needs of the commune's inhabitants and the gentle, rural tourism associated with the park. Finally, the obvious relationship of the buildings to the watercourse provided the link in this project.

The wealth of water-related heritage in Montalet-le-Bois - fountains, washhouses, mills - which we dug up in our historical research, supplemented by visits to the site, enabled us to decide that this small heritage deserved restoration and joint enhancement. The condition of these buildings, while not alarming, does call for special treatment. In fact, the large number of minor alterations observed, such as cracks and corrosion on metal parts, is a major cause for concern. The more serious pathologies encountered are common to all, and stem from a lack of maintenance of the buildings in recent years. Proliferation of biological colonies and dirt... It is therefore necessary to treat these disorders in order to achieve a healthy restoration.

We have decided to promote this small heritage by creating a hiking trail, passing through the various sites we have studied. These sites will be equipped with audio terminals and newspaper stands, enabling them to welcome walkers and locals alike, making them places of life within the commune. Our project runs from the spring washhouse to the mill wheel, following the watercourses to encompass the entire village center. The possibility that the neighboring plot could be used for parking spaces reinforced our idea and made our project possible. We also decided to include green energy production facilities. On the one hand, because it's in line with the current theme of environmental protection. Secondly, to give the mill wheel a new, more modern purpose, as its effective operation will guarantee its regular maintenance, since it will generate electricity. This production is intended to be self-consumed, thus reducing the village's environmental impact. The photovoltaic panels are also part of this same ecological approach.

The whole project, costing €828,909.46, seems feasible. Although the cost is high, it takes into account both the materials to be used and the labor involved. What's more, the costing does not include grants and subsidies from the PNR and the Yvelines département, which are already in contact with the commune and ready to finance part of the project.

In short, the discussions and debates that this project has provided within our group have enabled us to enrich and mobilize not only our knowledge, but also our critical faculties and positions, in order to reflect on a subject of significant preservation, restoration and enhancement. Our dialogue with the

commune of Montalet-le-Bois and the PNR du Vexin, to adapt and respond to their needs in this project, reinforces our desire to work in partnership with local communities to preserve and enhance their built heritage. We'll be in touch with them to find out more about the project that will be implemented in the commune and are enthusiastic about the idea of seeing the village revitalized through a heritage project.

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APPENDIX

Appendix no.1 : Montalet-le-Bois' map from *Monographie communales de l'instituteur*, 1899. (Archives départementales des Yvelines, 1T/Mono9[14])

Appendix no.2 : *La commune change, quand un ancien moulin à eau devient mairie*, Article from Le Décideur, n°2, Novembre 1987

Appendix no.3 : Graphic elements from Montalet-le-Bois ' PLUi

Appendix no.1 : Montalet-le-Bois' map from *Monographie communales de l'instituteur*, 1899. (Archives départementales des Yvelines, 1T/Mono9[14])

CONSTRUCTION

LA COMMUNE CHANGE, QUAND UN ANCIEN MOULIN A EAU DEVIENT MAIRIE...

Montalet-le-Bois connaît une mini-révolution. Pour cette commune de 149 habitants, le déménagement de ses services municipaux est un événement. La mairie troque un local de 25 m² contre un moulin à eau abandonné et restauré pour la circonstance.

Autrefois grenier à sel, puis moulin à eau, l'une des plus vieilles bâtisses du village de Montalet-le-Bois (Yvelines) vient d'être transformée en mairie. Située au cœur du village, elle était à l'abandon depuis bien longtemps. Le moulin subissait les outrages des ans : la toiture s'était effondrée, les murs de pierre s'effritaient et le propriétaire ne faisait rien pour améliorer les agressions du temps.

Un trop petit local

Or depuis bien longtemps le maire, M. BIESSE, le secrétaire de mairie et les conseillers municipaux se sentaient à l'étroit dans la petite salle de 25 m² qui accueille les services municipaux. La maison qu'elle occupe est également habitée par l'instituteur, et pour accéder aux archives (au grenier) ou bien au chauffage (en sous-sol), il faut traverser l'appartement du maître d'école !

L'on sait trop l'importance qu'a ce lieu collectif qu'est la mairie pour toute ville, quelle qu'en soit la taille. D'où l'intérêt porté à ce vieux moulin à eau, vaste bâtiment qui appartient au même titre que les collines et les ruisseaux au Vexin français. En outre, les habitants attendaient depuis longtemps une restauration de l'édifice devenu dangereux pour les promeneurs (le propriétaire avait été mis en demeure de pallier les risques). En lançant une opération de réhabilitation, il était fait d'une pierre deux coups.

Une difficulté de taille : l'expropriation

Novembre 1983 : une saisie immobilière est faite, suspendue en janvier 84 avant la vente aux enchères. La mairie se porte acquéreur. Le bâtiment est mis en réserve foncière d'équipement au mois de mai 1984, suite à une modification du P.O.S.

Le propriétaire de l'«Ancien Moulin» s'est déclaré vendeur, mais à un prix très élevé, correspondant au montant de ses hypothèques c'est-à-dire 350 000 F. Il a fallu passer par une enquête pour déclaration d'utilité publique, et la préfecture a donné un avis favorable le 6 mai 1985. Le Tribunal de

Grande Instance de Versailles a été saisi pour la procédure d'expropriation, il a rendu l'ordonnance d'expropriation le 5 novembre 1985. «Nous avons été déçus par la décision du tribunal puisqu'il n'a pas suivi le Commissaire du Gouvernement, lequel avait évalué le moulin à 105 000 F. Le TGI a rendu le jugement pour la somme de 285 144 F. Un prix très élevé ! » remarque M. BIESSE. «Nous regrettons en tout cas que les juges de droit privé soient si peu attentifs aux nécessités de petites communes, ils travaillent uniquement sur dossiers. C'est pour nous totalement préjudiciable...», ajoute le maire de Montalet-le-Bois.

Il est certain qu'en plus de cela d'énormes travaux sont nécessaires pour réhabiliter le moulin. Travaux qui coûtent fort cher.

Le problème du financement

«Nous ne pouvions envisager l'acquisition plus les travaux de remise en état et d'aménagement sans aide financière», explique le maire de Montalet. En effet, l'acquisition (285 144 F) ajoutée aux frais revenant à 295 000 F, il fallait compter un total de 378 000 F de dépenses H.T. puisque la remise en état du moulin se montait à 1 083 000 F.

«Or, nos moyens sont faibles», déclare M. BIESSE. Consultez pour preuve notre budget primitif pour 1987 : il est de 439 400 F».

L'obtention d'un contrat rural

«Nous avons donc constitué

les dossiers pour demander des subventions du Département et de la Région sous forme de contrat rural, explique M. BIESSE. Les deux assemblées ont été généreuses, puisque le Département a subventionné l'opération à 35 % et la Région à 45 % : le contrat a été signé le 7 juillet 1986. Sans ces aides précieuses, nous n'aurions pu envisager cette réhabilitation».

La commune a donc gardé à sa charge 20 % du coût de l'opération.

Réduire au minimum les dépenses de fonctionnement

Cette opération est sans doute la plus importante menée par ce village depuis bien longtemps. Mais, c'est une préoccupation du maire, il ne s'agit pas de négliger les autres travaux nécessaires pour tous : réfection des routes, installation du tout-à-l'égout...

En tout cas, pour réussir le montage financier, la commune a réduit au minimum ses dépenses de fonctionnement depuis 1977. Et comme il fallait économiser au mieux, M. BIESSE a établi tous les dossiers de procédure judiciaire, de demandes de subventions... De plus il a préparé soigneusement (photos à l'appui) un dossier pour participer au Concours de la Ligue Urbaine et Rurale pour l'Aménagement du cadre de la Vie Française*.

La question de l'assurance

Outre les difficultés rencontrées avec l'architecte, M. BIESSE évoque la question de l'assurance, problème auquel se heurtent les petites communes rurales qui se trouvent dans le même cas. «Nous avons dû prendre l'assurance dite «dommages-ouvrages»,

Fort heureusement, une subvention supplémentaire a été obtenue par Montalet : 90 000 ont été versés par le Comité départemental d'incitation à la création artistique.

Un luxe : la roue à eau

Les travaux ne sont pas encore tout à fait terminés, mais le gros-œuvre est achevé. La toiture a été refaite, en tuiles plates du pays, les murs intérieurs sont plâtrés, la belle bâtisse avance un air tranquille avec ses pierres quasi blanches et ses fenêtres capricieuses. Au rez-de-chaussée, en entrant, le secrétariat et le bureau du maire accueilleront les visiteurs. Une salle de réunion et une pièce pour les archives compléteront le bas de la nouvelle mairie.

A l'étage, une grande salle communale servira de lieu de réceptions et risque de connaître un franc succès auprès des habitants des villages voisins qui souhaiteront la louer !

Enfin, et bien que n'étant pas compris dans le marché, le Conseil municipal a décidé de remettre en service la roue à eau qui autrefois alimentait en électricité la commune. Un souci d'esthétique qui est presque un luxe pour Montalet. «Ce sera très joli», dit M. BIESSE avec un sourire. Une petite cascade sur le côté de la bâtisse, quel plaisir !»

Le Bernon — c'est le nom du bief qui fera tourner la roue — enchantera bientôt à nouveau le promeneur qui trouvera que décidément Montalet-le-Bois n'a pas que son nom pour faire rêver...

M.-P.S.

Ligue Urbaine et Rurale pour l'Aménagement du cadre de la Vie Française.

Association présidée par M. Xavier de CHRISTEN.

Chargé du concours : M. l'Amiral MATERRE.

8, rue de Montyon, 75008 Paris (tout près des Folies Bergères, haut-lieu de divertissement au nom champêtre...) - Tél. : 16 (1)

Chaque année, la Ligue organise ce concours qui concerne les villes de moins de 2 000 habitants. Son premier prix (40 000 F) récompense les maires ayant éliminé une construction inesthétique et l'ayant remplacée par une belle chose.

Appendix no.3 : Graphic elements from Montalet-le-Bois ' PLUi

PLU: Construire ensemble Grand Paris Seine & Oise

IV - REGLEMENT
Partie 5 - DISPOSITIONS GRAPHIQUES
5.2. Plans de zonage par commune
Montalet-le-Bois

Mars 2014
construireensemble.gpsae.fr